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Authors:	Patricia Sánchez-Blázquez
Revised by:	Armando Gil de Paz Ana Pérez Calpena Marisa García Vargas Jorge Iglesias Alfredo Montaña Mónica Relaño José Oñorbe
Approved by:	Patricia Sánchez-Blázquez

Distribution List:

Name	Affiliation	Date
Armando Gil de Paz	UCM	17/05/2023
Jorge Iglesias	IAA	17/05/2023
Mónica Relano	UGR	17/05/2023
Alfredo Montaña	INAOE	17/05/2023
José Oñorbe	US	17/05/2023

Acronyms:

ACT	Atacama Cosmology Telescope (ACT)
BCG	Brightest Cluster Galaxy
CAHA	Centro Astronómico Hispano en Andalucía
CATARSIS	Calar Alto Tetra-ARmed Super-Ifu spectrograph Survey
CGM	Circumgalactic Medium
CMB	Cosmic Microwave Background
CoD	Conceptual Design
DES	Dark Energy Survey
DLA	Damped Lyman Alpha
EM	Electromagnetic
ETG	Early-Type Galaxy
FoV	Field of View
GW	Gravitational Wave
HSC	Hyper-Suprime Cam
IA	Intrinsic Alignment
IFS	Integral-Field Spectrograph/Spectroscopy
IFU	Integral-Field Unit
IMF	Initial Mass Function
LAE	Lyman α emitter
LMT	Large Millimeter Telescope
LSS	Large Scale Structure
MAR	Mass Accretion Rate
MAH	Mass Accretion History
MUSE	Multi-Unit Spectroscopic Explorer
NFW	Navarro, Frenk & White (profile)
NS	Neutron Star
PD	Preliminary Design
PDF	Probability Distribution Functions
PI	Project Investigator
PM	Project Manager
PS	Project Scientist
PSF	Point Spread Function
RPS	Ram-Pressure Stripping
SDSS	Sloan Digital Sky Survey

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SED	Spectral Energy Distribution
SFG	Star-Forming Galaxy
SFH	Star Formation History
SFR	Star Formation Rate
SMBH	Supermassive Black Hole
SPT	South Pole Telescope
SSP	Simple/Single Stellar Population
SZ	Sunyaev-Zel'dovich
TARSIS	Tetra-ARm Super-Ifu Spectrograph
TTT	Tidal Torque Theory
WL	Weak Lensing

Change Control

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Reference Documents

N°	Document Name	Code
R.1	TARSIS. Operational Concept Document	TEC/TAR/003
R.2	TARSIS. Dithering and mapping strategies	TEC/TAR/009
R.3	TARSIS. Conceptual Design. Site. UV Characterization	TEC/TAR/008

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1. SUMMARY

The *Calar Alto Tetra-Armed Super-IFu spectrograph Survey*, CATARSIS, will survey 16 galaxy clusters in the redshift range $0.15 < z < 0.23$ to understand the formation of structures and the evolution of galaxies in a dynamic and growing environment. CATARSIS will sample each cluster from the center to $2xR_{200}$, obtaining 2D spectra in the TARSIS full spectral range (320-810 nm) of all the targets brighter than $m_{r,AB} = 22$ mag and galaxies with even fainter magnitudes but with emission line fluxes above $1-2 \times 10^{-17} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

There are two major far-reaching interests that motivate our understanding the population of galaxy clusters. Firstly, they are ideal test objects to check the likelihood of a given cosmological model to describe our Universe; secondly, they are very important probes of the astrophysical and chemical evolution of the baryonic component of the Universe (e.g. Rosati et al. [2002](#); Schuecker et al. [2003a,b](#); Voit [2005](#); Vikhlinin et al. [2003](#), [2009](#); Rozo et al. [2007](#); Henry et al. [2009](#); Mantz et al. [2008](#)). A good understanding and observational characterisation of galaxy clusters is required to attain these goals.

Furthermore, being a blind survey, CATARSIS has an important component of serendipitous science related to galaxies at high redshift. Due to the long exposure times, the large field of view (FoV) of TARSIS and its wavelength coverage, CATARSIS will be very competitive in the detection of high-redshift targets and, in particular, in the detection of Lyman- α emission at redshifts $1.63 < z < 3$, even when compared to other surveys using instruments in 8-m class telescopes.

This document describes the science cases of CATARSIS that motivated the instrument requirements of the instrument TARSIS. We will relate them to the state of the art, emphasizing those where we expect a more important contribution of CATARSIS. The document also outlines other science cases that, not being part of the survey, show the capabilities of TARSIS to improve our knowledge of a variety of astrophysical phenomena. The unique characteristics of this instrument ensure the scientific return of the CAHA observatory for the years to come.

2. GALAXY CLUSTERS AS COSMOLOGICAL PROBES

Galaxy clusters have been used for cosmology in a variety of ways, by e.g., *i*) measuring their gas fraction or mass-to-light ratio (e.g. Carlberg et al. [1996](#); Allen et al. [2008](#)), *ii*) using their X-ray luminosity function (e.g., Allen et al. [2002](#); Pierpaoli et al. [2003](#); Mantz et al. [2008](#)), *iii*) using information of their spatial distribution, through the Sunyaev-Zel'dovich (SZ) power spectrum/non-gaussianity and clustering analyses (e.g., Hong et al. [2012](#); Planck collaboration [2015](#); Bolliet et al. [2018](#); Marulli et al. [2018](#); note the increased relevance of such non-gaussianity studies to the light of the latest JWST results on the density of $z \gtrsim 8$ galaxies; see Biagetti et al. [2023](#) and references therein), or *iv*) estimating their abundances as a function of mass and redshift (e.g. Vikhlinin et al. [2009](#); Planck collaboration [2015](#); Bocquet et al. [2019](#); Costanzi et al. [2019](#)). The last two methods have gained prominence in recent years thanks to the increased size and/or depth of the cluster catalogues obtained from past or ongoing optical (SDSS, DES, HSC) or mm-wavelength surveys (Planck, ACT, SPT).

However, the accuracy of the cosmological constraints derived by these projects crucially depends on the accuracy with which cluster masses can be measured. Discrepancies between masses measured with different techniques can be as large as 30%, which will translate into errors.

Apart from the total mass, the mass profile contains invaluable information about the nature of dark matter and energy and the dynamical history of the clusters. Cold dark matter drives the dynamical evolution of structure shown in cosmological simulations and leads to specific predictions for the mass density profiles of DM halos, from galaxy to cluster scale. Significant deviations from these theoretical expectations would imply that the dynamical history of hierarchical formation of clusters does not proceed according to the Λ CDM paradigm, which could imply, for example, a non-standard contribution to the mass–energy density of the Universe at the epoch of cluster formation, or a dark matter particle of different nature.

CATARSIS observations will allow the determination of mass profiles with a much better precision than previous studies, overcoming the main biases affecting the determination of masses with two different techniques, the caustic and lensing, the only that do not need to assume dynamical equilibrium. Complementary observations with the Large Millimeter Telescope (LMT) TolTec camera (<http://toltec.astro.umass.edu/about.php>), will be used to measure the thermal structure of the intracluster medium (ICM) and the non-thermal motions. This analysis will result a much deeper understanding of the galaxy cluster physics which, in turn, will allow to calibrate the observations of ongoing or future statistical surveys.

2.1 The mass profile of galaxy clusters

The measurement of galaxy cluster masses is challenging, as most of the cluster mass is in the form of dark matter (DM). Mass estimation techniques thus probe the masses of clusters indirectly via the effect of the gravitational potential of the cluster on its ICM, its member galaxies, or on the images of background galaxies.

Using different methods to determine cluster mass profiles is fundamental since different methods suffer from different systematics. For instance, determinations of cluster masses using the emission of the hot ICM use the expected temperature for gas is in hydrostatic equilibrium and tend to be underestimated if bulk gas motions and the complex thermal structure of the Intra-Cluster Medium (ICM) are ignored (Rasia et al. [2005](#), [2006](#); Lau et al. [2009](#); Molnar et al. 2010; Cavaliere et al. 2011). Cluster triaxiality, substructures and interlopers tend to bias the mass profile estimates obtained with gravitational lensing methods (e.g. Meneghetti et al. [2011](#); Becker & Kravtsov [2011](#); Feroz & Hobson [2012](#)) while triaxiality and substructures in the velocity space are the main biases for determination of cluster masses using galaxy kinematics (Cen [1997](#); Biviano et al. [2006](#); Foex et al. [2017](#)).

2.1.1 Strong lensing

Galaxy cluster cores contain large concentrations of dark matter, and in such act as powerful gravitational lenses. At its strongest, the deflection of light rays from distant galaxies can create multiple images of a single source (Kneib & Natarajan [2011](#)), and the location of such multiples can be used to infer the mass distribution in cluster cores (Richard et al. [2010](#); Zitrin et al. [2012](#)). An important part of the mass modelling relies on getting accurate spectroscopic redshifts for the lensed sources, to completely confirm the lensing system and to avoid degeneracies in the mass

normalisation. As the typical magnitude range for lensed sources found with Hubble is $\sim 23\text{-}25$ AB mag (Richard et al. 2009; Jauzac et al. 2014a), deep spectroscopy is required. Large spectroscopic campaigns have been performed with multi-object spectrographs (Johnson et al. 2014; Grillo et al. 2014), but they rely on a preselection based on deep multi-band Hubble images and are quite inefficient since all multiple images are crowded in the cluster core.

The advantage of using an integral field spectrograph (IFS) was demonstrated by Richard et al. (2014) in their study of the inner mass profile of the lensing cluster SMACSJ2031.8-4036 at $z = 0.331$, where they were able to measure the redshift of 12 systems at z from $z = 1.46$ to 6.4 , using the $[\text{OII}]\lambda\lambda 3726, 3729\text{\AA}$ and Lyman- α emission. The increased number of multiple images allowed them to obtain the mass in the inner profile with a precision of a few percent, about 5 times better than previous models (see Figure 1).

Six clusters in the CATARSIS golden have multiple images and extended arcs in their cores. In the above study, only half of the 12 systems detected have Ly- α fluxes above our detection limit. However, while this transition can only be observed in targets at $z > 2.9$ with MUSE, it will be detectable at $z \gtrsim 1.6$ using TARSIS. Therefore, the number of multiple systems that we expect to find using TARSIS is higher than in this work.

Figure 1: Projected cluster mass profile in the central parts of the SE galaxy cluster (red curve). The radial distance of all multiple images used as strong-lensing constraints are marked with black ticks. The range of mass profiles allowed by the previous mass model (with redshifts obtained with long slit or multi-object spectrographs), is marked in green, showing the gain in precision obtained with the IFS data.

2.1.2 Weak lensing

Weak gravitational lensing is responsible for the weak shape distortion, or shear, and magnification of the images of background sources due to the gravitational field of intervening massive objects and large scale structure (Bartelmann et al. 2001; Umetsu 2010; Hoekstra 2013; Mandelbaum 2018). Weak shear lensing by galaxy clusters gives rise to levels of up to a few 10 percent of elliptical distortions in images of background sources. Thus, the weak shear lensing signal, as measured from small but coherent image distortions in galaxy shapes, can provide a direct measure of the projected mass distribution of galaxy clusters under the assumption that there is no spatial correlation between the intrinsic shapes of the galaxies (e.g., Kaiser and Squires 1993; Fahlman et al. 1994; Okabe and Umetsu 2008).

Weak gravitational lensing allows us to directly access the projected surface mass density of clusters largely independently of their dynamical state or through assumptions on complex baryonic physics (Umetsu 2020). In real observations, however, contamination of the background sample by unlensed galaxies (Hoekstra 2003; Hoekstra et al. 2011), uncertainties on the lens parametrization (Clowe et al. 2004; Corless & King 2007), and triaxiality of the DM halo are sources of substantial systematic errors. Furthermore, the technique relies on the assumption that no intrinsic alignments between the galaxies and the DM halo are present.

Figure 2: Measurement error in the determination of M_{200} (upper panels) and c (lower panels) as a function of the maximum fitted radius θ_{\max} for three clusters at a redshift of $z = 0.3$. The results were obtained by fitting an NFW profile to the simulated tangential shear profile, with M_{200} and c as free parameters. The uncertainties are determined from 1000 realisations. The solid lines indicate the total uncertainty, whereas the dashed line denotes the contribution by large scale structure (LSS), and the dotted line the contribution from the intrinsic ellipticities of the background galaxies.

Figure 2 shows the uncertainty in the determination of the total mass and concentration parameter as a function of the maximum fitted angular radius derived by Hoekstra (2002) using numerical simulations. The figure shows that intrinsic alignments can be an important source of biases when the fit is only done using central data, but it is dominated by the presence of other structures along the line of sight when larger areas are fitted. This major source of uncertainty will be highly reduced in the determinations made with CATARSIS data, as we will have, at the very least, redshifts for all the objects in the FoV brighter than $m_{r,AB} < 22$ mag. Furthermore, we will also be able to study the intrinsic alignments of galaxies with the DM thanks to our 2D kinematic information (see Section 2.4).

2.1.3 Dynamic of galaxies

Using their total dispersion, their dispersion profiles, and/or their escape velocity profile, we can infer cluster masses based on the virial theorem, the Jeans relation for a collision-less fluid, or the Caustic technique. While the first two also rely on the assumption of dynamical equilibrium, the Caustic technique principles apply to all the clusters, independently of their dynamical state.

The Caustic technique (Diaferio & Geller [1997](#); Diaferio [1999](#); Serra et al. [2011](#); Gifford et al. [2013](#)) takes the positions and velocities of a galaxy cluster’s member galaxies and projects them into a phase space of cluster-centric radius and line-of-sight velocity. As galaxies fall towards the cluster, they form a coherent infall pattern extending out to 10-20 Mpc from the cluster, they are accelerated by the gravitational potential of the cluster, reaching a maximal velocity as they pass through the cluster for the first time. They then ultimately become virialized members, orbiting on bound orbits around the cluster. This behavior produces the characteristic "trumpet"-shaped caustic profile of galaxies infalling and orbiting around a massive (see Figure 3).

Like for the lensing measurements, caustic masses are independent of the dynamical state of the cluster and are insensitive to the physical processes that might cause the hydrostatic biases. The main uncertainties come from asymmetries in the shape of the clusters, the presence of substructure and, above all, the anisotropy in the velocity of galaxies, defined as $\beta \equiv 1 - \sigma_t^2 / \sigma_r^2$, where σ_t^2 and σ_r^2 represent the tangential and radial velocity dispersion components, respectively. Most authors use a constant value at all radii $\langle \beta \rangle = 0.2 \pm 0.2$, extracted from numerical simulations, but this assumption can lead to an overestimation of the mass in the central parts of the clusters ($r < 0.6 R_{200}$; Diaferio [1999](#); Serra et al. [2011](#)).

Figure 3: Schematic view of the orbit of an infalling galaxy in phase space. The orbital sequence is indicated by lines and arrows. The area under the influence of the cluster potential is shaded in gray. When galaxies fall into the cluster for the first time, they approach from the right side of region A, occupying the region of high velocity at small to intermediate radius. After the first core crossing, galaxies come out from the left side of region A to the B, and then backslash to region C (beyond R_{200} in some cases). Then they repeatedly infall and outfall until they settle into the central region of the cluster, while virializing within the potential well. Some galaxies may violently plunge deep inside the cluster, approaching the cluster core quite closely, during the first infall or while virializing.

Further biases come from the details of the sample selection. To first order, galaxies dynamically respond to the influence of the Newtonian gravitational potential, regardless of their luminosities, shapes, colors, or star-formation histories. Yet galaxies traveling within a cluster environment are likely to have had one or more localized and short-lived gravitational interactions over its lifetime. This “dynamical friction” alters the total cluster velocity distribution away from its simple Newtonian expectations. This will be more evident if we use the velocity distribution of galaxies that had fallen into the cluster at earlier times as they will show this effect the hardest.

The expense of obtaining spectroscopic redshifts places limitations on acquiring velocities for a complete sample of cluster members. In practical terms, luminous galaxies are often prioritised ahead of fainter ones, and photometric preselection may also result in the preferential selection of red over blue galaxies. However, numerical simulations have shown that when only bright and red galaxies are used for dynamical determinations, there is a bias between the halo and galaxy cluster velocity dispersion on the order of $\sigma_{\text{gal}}/\sigma_{\text{DM}} \sim 0.87\text{-}0.95$, and a distinct difference in the stacked galaxy and DM particle velocities distribution. The systematic underestimation of the velocity dispersions increases when imposing brighter absolute magnitude cuts and can reach values up to 35% in some clusters, indicating that dynamical friction is a serious source of bias if we only use these galaxies as tracers of the underlying gravitational potential. This is illustrated in Figure 4, that shows the bias in the velocity dispersion of red galaxies as a function of the magnitude limit of the sample in different haloes (Old et al. 2013).

The determination of the caustic is also dependent on the number of redshifts and the spatial distribution of the galaxies. This can be seen in Figure 5, where we show the cumulative mass as a function of radius measured with the caustic method (Gifford et al. 2013) for a massive cluster at $z = 0.237$ of the Three Hundred numerical simulations (Cui et al. 2018). Different profiles indicate the effect of different magnitude and color cuts. Foex et al. (2017) have shown that in order to obtain unbiased masses a minimum of 50 galaxies homogeneously distributed and randomly selected are needed, and the magnitude limit of the sample has to reach, at least, $m^* + 1$, where m^* is the magnitude measure for an L^* galaxy at the distance of the cluster.

Figure 4: The evolution of the velocity dispersion of the semi-analytic clusters at $z = 0$ with brighter absolute I-band magnitude limits, i.e., excluding fainter galaxies. Note that member galaxies are selected within the halo R_{200} . The velocity dispersion is normalized by the halo velocity dispersion and the clusters are binned according to halo M_{200} . The error bars signify the standard error on the mean of clusters included in each cluster mass bin. A brighter adopted I-band magnitude limit leads to an increasingly underestimated cluster velocity dispersion, a result that is more severe for clusters with lower halo mass (from Old et al. 2013).

Figure 5: Cumulative mass as a function of radius obtained running the public code *causpy* (Gifford et al. 2003) with the redshift of a cluster at $z = 0.247$ from the Three Hundred project (Cui et al. 2018). The figure illustrates the different profiles recovered by the code for different cuts in magnitude and color.

CATARSIS will obtain redshifts for all the galaxies in the FoV brighter than $m_{r,AB} \sim 22$ mag, avoiding biases towards any galaxy type. Furthermore, our measurements will not suffer from spatial incompleteness derived from specific observational set-ups (e.g., caused by fiber collision of slit positioning) which are known to be the source of can cause a spatially dependent incompleteness of the spectroscopic sample, and induces an error in the caustic determination of the caustic.

We have used the most massive group in the Illustris TNG300 cosmological simulations (Springel et al. 2018) to calculate the expected number of galaxies with $m_{r,AB} < 22$ mag and compare them with number of redshifts obtained by the Hectospec survey (HeCS, Rines et al. 2013), and the SDSS (including BOSS) surveys. This comparison can be seen in Figure 6, for a cluster at $z = 0.15$. Numbers are calculated inside three different radii and plotted as a function of clusters size. Thanks to its large FoV, TARSIS/CATARSIS will obtain redshifts for a much large number of galaxies than ongoing surveys, allowing a much finer analysis and quantifying the systematics derived of a biased sample selection. These numbers are a lower limit, as we have not included those with emission lines. **Figure 7** shows the cluster members as a function of the $H\alpha$ and $[OII]\lambda\lambda 3726, 3729\text{\AA}$ luminosity compared with the one in r -band magnitude.

Figure 6: Number of cluster members inside spheres of radius = R_{200} (green), $1.36 \times R_{200}$ (blue) and $3 \times R_{200}$ (black) in Illustris TNG300. The number of members is plotted as a function of the virial radius of the cluster at $z = 0.15$. The cyan arrows represent the number of spectroscopic members in the first data release of HeCS cluster redshift survey, while the yellow ones, the number of members with spectra in the CATARSIS mother sample.

Figure 7: Number of galaxies in clusters at $z = 0.15$ (top panels) and $z = 0.20$ (bottom panels) as a function of the H α luminosity (left), [OII] luminosity (central) and r-band magnitude (right) in Illustris TNG300 cosmological simulations. Different colors represent the averages for clusters with different virial radius, as indicated in the insets.

As mentioned before, using different methods to determine cluster mass profiles is fundamental since different methods suffer from different systematics. For instance, ICM determinations of cluster masses assumes the gas is in hydrostatic equilibrium and tend to be underestimated if bulk gas motions and the complex thermal structure of the Intra-Cluster Medium (ICM) are ignored (Rasia et al. 2004, 2006; Lau et al. 2009; Molnar et al. 2010; Cavaliere et al. 2011). Cluster triaxiality, substructures and interlopers tend to bias the mass profile estimates obtained by gravitational lensing (e.g. Meneghetti et al. 2011; Becker & Kravtsov 2011; Feroz & Hobson 2012) while triaxiality and substructures in the velocity space are the main biases for cluster galaxy kinematics (Cen 1997; Biviano et al. 2006) analysis. Comparing different mass profile determinations can therefore help assessing the contribution of nonthermal pressure to the ICM

and the elongation along the line-of-sight (e.g., Morandi & Limousin [2012](#); Sereno et al. [2012](#)). If systematics are well under control, the comparison of independent determinations of cluster mass profiles from gravitational lensing and the kinematics of cluster members can shed light on the very nature of DM (Faber & Visser [2006](#); Serra & Domínguez Romero [2011](#)).

2.2 The nature of dark matter

Uncovering the nature of dark matter (DM) is one of the major goals of science in the 21st century. The standard cosmological model, Λ CDM, assumes that DM particles are collisionless, which is to say that the only DM interactions relevant for structure formation are gravitational. Self-interacting dark matter (SIDM) is an interesting alternative to CDM where DM particles can scatter with one another at astrophysically important rates.

2.2.1 The inner mass profile

A non-vanishing DM self-interaction probability would impact the internal structure of halos, as collisional processes transport heat across high-density regions, thereby homogenizing the mass distribution and flattening the observed profiles in the cores of halos (Yoshida et al. [2000](#); Rocha et al. [2013](#); Robertson et al. [2019](#), [2021](#)). Self-interacting dark matter (SIDM) was proposed as a possible to the core-cusp problem in dwarf spheroidal galaxies (see Tulin & Yu [2018](#) for a review). SIDM cross sections in the range $\sigma/m \sim 1 - 5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ would produce central densities in broad agreement with the values observed in dwarf galaxies (e.g., Spergel & Steinhardt [2000](#); Davé et al. [2001](#); Valli & Yu [2018](#); Ren et al. [2019](#)). SIDM also provides a potential solution to the observed diversity of galaxy rotation curves (Kamada et al. [2017](#); Creasey et al. [2017](#); Ren et al. [2019](#); Kahlhoefer et al. [2019](#); Sameie et al. [2020](#); see, however, Santos-Santos et al. [2020](#)) and the anti-correlation between Milky Way satellites' pericentric distances and their central densities (Kaplinghat et al. [2019](#); Correa [2020](#)). Evidence for a large DM–DM scattering cross-section would rule out many popular DM candidates and would therefore alter the most promising regions of DM parameter space at which to target direct and indirect detection experiments (Zentner [2009](#); Kaplinghat et al. [2014](#); Boddy et al. [2014](#); Kouvaris et al. [2015](#); Del Nobile et al. [2015](#)). These tests however require a very accurate determination of the mass density profile of a representative sample of clusters over a wide radial range, from kpc to Mpc scales.

CATARSIS observations will allow to improve the determination of inner mass profiles using strong lensing techniques (Section 2.1.1), and it will complement these measurements with dynamical measurements (Section 2.1.3). The advantage of CATARSIS observations for the determination of masses with these two methodologies have been outlined above, and they should result in errors below a few percent.

2.2.2 Anisotropy in the velocity distribution of DM haloes

The three-dimensional shape of collisionless halos is predicted to be generally triaxial with a preference for prolate shapes (Warren et al. [1992](#); Jing & Suto [2002](#)), reflecting the collisionless nature of DM (Ostriker & Steinhardt [2003](#)). Older halos tend to be more relaxed and thus to be rounder. Since more massive halos form later, on average, cluster-size halos are expected to be more elongated than less massive systems (Shaw et al. [2006](#); Ho et al. [2006](#); Despali et al. [2014](#), [2017](#); Bonamigo et al. [2015](#)). Accretion of matter from the surrounding large-scale environment also plays a key role in determining the shape and orientation of halos. The halo orientation tends

to be in the preferential infall direction of the subhalos and hence aligned along the surrounding filaments (Shaw et al. [2006](#)). The shape and orientation of galaxy clusters thus provide an independent test of models of structure formation. The DM velocity anisotropy profile also holds important information about the nature of DM, such as its collisionless nature (e.g., Host et al. [2009](#)) and decaying time (Peter, Moody, & Kamionkowski [2010](#)). N-body simulations using CDM suggest a nearly universal velocity anisotropy profile (Cole & Lacey [1996](#); Carlberg et al. [1997](#); Colin, Klypin, & Kravtsov [2000](#); Diemand, Moore, & Stadel [2004](#); Rasia et al. [2004](#); Wojtak et al. [2005](#)), where β increases radially from zero in the central region to roughly 0.5 in the outer region (Carlberg et al. [1997](#); Cole & Lacey [1996](#); Hansen & Moore [2006](#)). For collisional systems, in contrast, the velocity anisotropy is explicitly zero in the equilibrated regions.

The velocity anisotropy of a DM is defined by the β parameter as $\beta \equiv 1 - \sigma_t^2/\sigma_r^2$, where σ_t^2 and σ_r^2 are the 1-dimensional tangential and radial velocity dispersions in a spherical system (Binney & Tremaine [1987](#)). Efforts to measure the DM velocity anisotropy have been done using the ICM temperature, a method which is applicable at intermediate radii and relaxed systems (Host et al. [2009](#)), or by examining galaxy velocities (Lemze et al. [2011](#)), with constrains on the self-interaction cross-section per unit mass of $\sigma/m \lesssim 1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$.

2.3 Substructure in galaxy clusters

The presence of substructures can substantially affect the estimate of the cluster velocity dispersion and mass (Girardi et al. [1996](#); Pinkney et al. [1996](#)) but, on the other hand, it can provide insights into the formation process of the cluster, and the expansion rate of the Universe (Richstone et al. [1992](#); Kauffmann & White [1993](#); Mohr et al. [1995](#); Thomas et al. [1998](#)).

From an astrophysical point of view, the mass growth of clusters brings new (generally gas-rich) galaxy populations into clusters (e.g., Moran et al. [2007](#)) and may lead to shock heating of the ICM and/or disruption of cooling in cluster cores (e.g., Poole et al. [2008](#)). The presence of substructures appears to be a fundamental ingredient of the galaxy-environment connection and for shaping the morphology-density relation (e.g., Fasano et al. [2015](#); Girardi et al. [2015](#)). Reliable measurements and interpretation of cluster substructure are, therefore, of broad interest.

The identification of substructure has been done using X-ray surface brightness morphology to either separate relaxed from merging clusters (e.g., Parekh et al. [2015b](#)) or to quantify the systematic errors affecting cluster mass measurements (Nagai et al. [2007](#); Piffaretti & Valdarnini [2008](#)). The substructure identification with X-rays is limited to the cluster central region within the R_{500} radius, which is the typical largest distance where the ICM can be detected reliably (Piffaretti & Valdarnini [2008](#)), and to substructures that contain a quantity of hot gas large enough to produce a detectable X-ray emission. In addition, the identification of substructures is complicated by the fact that viscosity and magnetic fields can displace the hot gas from the dominant mass distribution, as indicated by the observations of numerous merging clusters (e.g., Markevitch et al. [2004](#); Mahdavi et al. [2007](#); Menanteau et al. [2012](#)).

The existence of substructures in the DM halos of clusters can also be revealed by the anomalous images of strong gravitational lensing systems (Kneib et al. [1996](#); Mao & Schneider [1998](#); Mao et al. [2004](#)) or by peculiar features of the halo density profiles of weak lensing systems (Hoekstra et al. [2000](#); Clowe et al. [2006](#); Okabe et al. [2010](#); Pastor Mira et al. [2011](#); Oguri et al. [2013](#);

McCleary et al. 2015; Shirasaki 2015), although the contamination by chance alignments of unrelated massive systems along the line of sight can be severe (Hoekstra 2003; Hoekstra et al. 2011; Geller et al. 2013).

The redshift distribution of member galaxies exposes substructure in the form of asymmetrical velocity distributions and dynamically distinct subgroups (e.g., Dressler & Shectman 1988; Hou et al. 2012; Cohn 2012; Einasto et al. 2012). Not only does this type of analysis offer key insights into the dynamical state of cluster, but it also provides an estimate of cluster mass. However, the Caustic techniques offers a more promising avenue, not only to detect substructure, but to measure their masses. Yu et al. (2015) tested the Caustic technique as a substructure detector on two samples of 150 mock redshift surveys of clusters with M_{200} masses in the range between $M_{200} \sim (10^{14} - 10^{15}) h^{-1} M_{\odot}$ using a large cosmological N-body simulation of a Λ CDM model.

Figure 8: Completeness vs. 3D substructure mass for three different N_{3R} (randomly selected redshifts in the FoV, including clusters and no cluster galaxies) in clusters with a median mass $M_{200} = 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ using the Caustic methodology. The error bars show the deviation for different random selections of the redshifts (from Yu et al. 2015).

The success of the method to identify substructures depend on the mass of the cluster, the mass of the structures, and the number of available redshifts for galaxy members. Figure 8 illustrates this by showing the completeness in the identification of structures in a cluster of $10^{14} M_{\odot}$ as a function of the structure mass for different number of redshifts (N_{3R}) randomly selected in the FoV of a cluster at $z = 0.2$.

Deep observations using TARSIS will allow the detection and characterization of small structures in the CATARSIS cluster sample. The main requirement is having redshifts for a large and unbiased number of galaxies with a homogeneous distribution in the whole area. The expected errors in the line-of-sight velocities are very small compared to the velocity dispersion of the cluster and the cluster structures, and they will not add important sources of errors.

2.4 Galaxy alignments

The cosmic web is shaped by the gravitational tidal field, which determines the directions of anisotropic mass collapse. The same tidal field is also responsible for spinning up haloes and galaxies. For example, during the linear phase of structure formation, the tidal torque theory (TTT; Hoyle 1949; Peebles 1969; Doroshkevich 1970; White 1984) describes how the angular

momentum of a proto-halo is generated by the gravitational shear of the surrounding matter distribution. This produce that galaxy shapes are not randomly oriented, rather they are statistically aligned in a way that can depend on formation environment, history, and galaxy type. Studying the alignment of galaxies can, therefore, deliver important information about the physics of galaxy formation and evolution as well as the growth of structure in the universe. In particular, the current paradigm states that galaxies acquire their angular momentum by the torque exerted from large-scale structure onto the protogalactic object prior to gravitational collapse (Hoyle 1949). The angular momentum, which is conserved during collapse, will align with the filaments, but only for galaxies below a certain mass.

Figure 9: Expected alignments in the TTT between the spin of disc & early-type galaxies and the filaments.

Indeed, high-mass haloes have spins preferentially perpendicular to filaments while low-mass haloes show the opposite trend, with their spins being preferentially parallel to filaments (e.g., Navarro et al. 2004; Aragón-Calvo et al. 2014). The halo mass at which this transition happens is known as the *spin-flip transition mass*, or, in short, *spin-flip mass*. This transition mass increases with decreasing redshift (e.g., see Codis et al. 2012; Wang & Kang 2018) and is $\sim 1 \times 10^{12} h^{-1} M_{\odot}$ at present day.

The results from the observations are not so clear, despite the large number of studies in the literature (e.g., Trujillo et al. 2006; Wang et al. 2018, to cite a few). Some suggest that spiral galaxies are aligned perpendicular to filaments, in agreement with predictions from cosmological simulations based on the Λ CDM model (Lee & Pen 2002; Lee & Erdogdu 2007; Jones et al. 2010; Zhang et al. 2015), while others find just the opposite (e.g., Tempel et al. 2013; Tempel & Libeskind 2013; Pahwa et al. 2016).

The study of alignments can also give us some insights into the nature of DM. Despite the success of the cold and collisionless DM paradigm (CDM), we know very little about its particle nature, other than its interactions with the Standard Model (protons, neutrons, neutrinos, etc.) must be exceptionally weak. Interestingly, the self-interaction of dark matter is not constrained by the same limits and provides a unique avenue to understand forces within the dark sector without having to assume any coupling to the Standard Model (for a review see Tulin & Yu 2018).

Recently, it has been shown that the intrinsic alignments of galaxies are sensitive to the nature of DM up to scales of several Mpc/h. Using hydrodynamical simulations with different models of self-interaction, Katz et al. (2018) have showed that the differences should be detectable at a 5σ level and it could be recognized due to its dependency with halo mass and cluster-centric distance.

Furthermore, as we mentioned before, the study of “*intrinsic alignments*” (IA) of galaxies with overdensities is crucial as it represents a major contaminant of weak lensing cosmic shear studies, which rely on the assumption that galaxies are randomly oriented (Hirata & Seljak 2004; Bridle & King 2007; Kirk et al. 2010, 2012; Krause et al. 2016). Frameworks to mitigate the impact of IA on cosmological model inference have been developed, whereby nuisance parameters can be marginalised over (King 2005; Joachimi et al. 2011). This requires insights into the origin of the intrinsic alignments signal (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Sketch of the gravitational lensing signal and its IA contamination. Light travels from the top of the sketch downwards, from the source plane, via the lens plane, to the plane at the bottom, containing the images as seen by an observer. The matter structure (green ellipsoid) deflects the light from the background source galaxies (blue discs) and distorts their images tangentially with respect to the apparent center of the lens (as seen in the bottom plane). Consequently, the galaxy images become aligned (GG signal). Galaxies which are physically close to the lens structure (red ellipsoids) may be subjected to forces that cause them to point towards the structure, which results in the alignment of their images. Images of galaxies close to the lens are then preferentially anti-aligned with the gravitationally sheared images of background galaxies (from Joachimi et al. 2016).

Measuring alignments have been usually analysed using galaxy images by assuming that galaxies spin along their minor axis. However, due to projection effects, it is not possible to know which half of the two in which the galaxy is divided by its major axis, is closer to the observer, so it is not straightforward to measure the 3D orientation of the galaxy's angular momentum. To deal with this problem some authors take all the possible directions and average the results while others just take one possibility, plaguing the results with uncertainties. Thanks to the 2D spectroscopy provided by TARSIS, we will be able to obtain a coarse velocity field, that will be enough, if galaxies have trailing spiral arms, to determine, unambiguously, the real alignment of galaxies.

The study of alignments between galaxies and filaments requires to know the rotational direction of galaxies with respect to the line of sight. TARSIS minimum requirements, with a pixel size of 2 arcsec and spectral resolution of $R \sim 1000$ is enough to obtain the 2D velocity field. To illustrate this, we resampled MUSE observations of NGC6902 to these values and convolved it with a PSF

of 1-arcsec FWHM. We then run Ppxf (Cappellari & Emsellem 2004) to measure line-of-sight velocities. **Figure 11** shows the results, demonstrating that it is possible to measure the galaxies' global rotation pattern using CATARSIS observations. Furthermore, it is also possible to build maps of emission line fluxes and line-strength indices. Even if the resolution is not very high, these measurements will be invaluable to understanding the physical processes that influence the

evolution of galaxies in clusters (see Section 3.1.1).

Figure 11: Line-of-sight velocity map for nearby galaxy NGC 6902 (see direct image in the top-left corner) shifted to the CATARSIS limiting redshift of $z = 0.23$ (right), and as it was observed with the TARSIS instrument, for three different spaxel scales. The thin-disk modelling results ($a \propto V_{max}$, $v = V_{sys} - V_{z=0.23}$, $pa = \text{position angle}$) for the TARSIS spaxels ($\sim 2 \times 2 \text{ arcsec}^2$) is shown in the upper right corner.

2.5 Mass Accretion Rates (MAR)

In the current model of the formation of cosmic structure, where DM halos form from the aggregation of smaller halos, the MAR of dark matter halos is a stochastic process whose average behavior can be predicted with N-body simulations (e.g., van den Bosch 2002). In principle, the MAR of dark matter halos is a valuable tool for testing different models of structure formation. Specifically, the mass evolution $M(z)$ of a DM halo, which describes its mass assembling history, or its time derivative, the mass accretion rate $\dot{M}(z)$ can be used to test the predictions of the Λ CDM cosmological model, i.e., MAR should be correlated with halo properties, including concentration (Tasitsiomi et al. 2004; Zhao et al. 2009; Giocoli et al. 2012; Ludlow et al. 2013), shape (Kasun & Evrard 2005; Allgood et al. 2006; Bett et al. 2007; Ragone-Figueroa et al. 2010); spin (Vitvitska et al. 2002; Bett et al. 2007), degree of internal relaxation (Power et al. 2012), and fraction of substructures (Gao et al. 2004; van den Bosch et al. 2005; Ludlow et al. 2013). The model also predicts a correlation with the halo formation redshift (Lacey & Cole 1993; van den Bosch 2002; Ragone-Figueroa et al. 2010; Giocoli et al. 2012).

The mass accretion history (MAH) can be a probe of the cosmological parameters. Hurier (2019) uses the thermal Sunyaev-Zel'dovich (SZ) effect as a proxy for the mass of the clusters from the 2nd Planck SZ catalogue (Planck Collaboration et al. 2016) and the fit by Correa et al. (2015) to the MAH of dark matter halos in simulations to derive values for the power-spectrum

normalization (σ_8), the cosmic mass density (Ω_m), and the Hubble parameter (H_0), which result in $\sigma_8(\Omega_m/0.3) - 0.3 (H_0/70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}) - 0.2 = 0.75 \pm 0.06$. This value is in rough agreement with other analyses of galaxy cluster samples and of the power spectrum of the cosmic microwave background (de Haan et al. [2016](#); Planck Collaboration VI [2020](#); Zubeldia & Challinor [2019](#)).

A unique probe of the mass assembly of galaxy clusters relies on the observational detection of their edges. Examining the logarithmic slope of the cluster halo profile highlights a density jump at the location where recently accreted material is reaching its first apocenter, associated with the last density caustic (Bertschinger [1985](#)) density profile of both matter and galaxies, termed the splashback radius. This radius, that correspond to the location of the first orbital apocenter of satellite galaxies after their infall, offers a robust way to gain insight into dynamics properties of the halo and to the nature of DM itself. In Λ CDM, the location of the splashback radius or the turnaround radius crucially depend upon the MAR of the collapsing halo (Vogelsberger et al. [2011](#); Diemer & Kravtsov [2014](#); Adhikari et al. [2014](#)). For halos of the same mass, large accretion rate results in a smaller splashback radius (see Shim & Diemer [2023](#) and references therein). The physical reason is simple: the deeper the halo potential well gets during the orbit of a DM particle, the smaller is the value of its apocenter.

A change of slope that is consistent with the expectations from the simulations is indeed present in the profile of the surface number density of galaxies from the Dark Energy Survey (DES) cross-correlated with the SZ clusters from the South Pole Telescope (SPT) and the Atacama Cosmology Telescope (ACT) (Shin et al. [2019](#)), as well as in the deprojected cross-correlation of the SZ clusters from the Planck Survey with galaxies detected photometrically in the PanSTARRS survey (Zürcher & More [2019](#)). Similarly, the splashback radius is detected in the inferred DM density profiles of the redMaPPer clusters (More et al. [2016](#)) and in clusters from either SDSS (Baxter et al. [2017](#)) or DES (Chang et al. [2018](#)). Although interlopers along the line of sight affect the inference of this feature both from optically-selected clusters (Busch & White [2017](#); Shin et al. [2019](#); Sunayama & More [2019](#)) and from weak lensing analyses of X-ray selected clusters (Umetsu & Diemer [2017](#); Contigiani et al. [2019](#)), galaxy redshift surveys covering the whole area of interest, like CATARSIS, can overcome the effects of this contamination and constrain the relation between the splashback radius and the accretion rate (Xhakaj et al. [2020](#)).

Furthermore, while the splashback radius is observed as a feature in the spatial distribution of matter and galaxies (and their velocities), it also has an inherent timescale associated with it: the time for a particle or galaxy to reach the apocenter of its first orbit. In other words, DM particles or galaxies that form the splashback region have been inside the halo for approximately one orbital time, from accretion to first apocenter. Unlike DM particles, galaxy properties like star formation rates (SFRs) and morphology can evolve significantly on similar timescales if the cluster environment plays a role in galaxy evolution. Since the splashback feature is closely related to the orbital time it is possible to use it as a clock to study different populations of galaxies and their time-evolving properties.

The MAR can also be derived in more model independent way. Beyond the splashback radius, the velocity of the DM within a radial shell reaches a minimum, and so most closely represent the infall of new material onto the cluster (De Boni et al. [2016](#)). Therefore, assuming an infall velocity (e.g., one based on a spherical-collapse model) is, in principle, possible, to derive the MAR. Diaferio & Geller ([1997](#)) applied this method to numerical simulations obtaining very good agreement. To derive MARs, however, it is necessary to obtain a good coverage of redshifts in

the external parts, which is very rare in studies using multi-object spectrographs (see also Rines et al. [2013](#)).

Figure 12: Relation between the splashback radius and the accretion rate predicted by three different cosmological simulations based on the Λ CDM model.

2.6 Intracluster Light

The most revealing signature of galaxy cluster assembly is contained within a diffuse component occupying the space between the galaxies in clusters. This component is composed of a substantial fraction of stars (5–20% of the total light of the cluster, Krick & Bernstein [2007](#)) that constitute the so-called intra-cluster light (ICL, see Mihos [2016](#) for a review). This diffuse light is thought to form primarily by galaxies that interact with the cluster medium or merge during the hierarchical accretion history of the cluster (e.g., Gregg & West [1998](#); Mihos et al. [2005](#); Conroy et al. [2007](#); Presotto et al. [2014](#); Contini et al. [2014](#)). The amount of ICL, stellar population properties (age, metallicity) and the spatial variation of the ICL are the results of the assembly history of the cluster (Rudick et al. [2010](#)), and that is why its analysis is crucial.

Different physical mechanisms may be at play in the formation of the ICL, and their relative importance can vary during the dynamical history of the cluster and at different mass ranges. Therefore, the fraction of light in this component and the evolution with redshift will provide information of the efficiency of the interactions that form the ICL. The determination of the mass fraction of this component can also help to alleviate the tension between the observed growth rate of brightest cluster galaxies (around 2 in the last 7-8 Gyr) and that expected in theoretical models based on a Λ CDM cosmology (3–4 since $z=1$, de Lucia & Blaizot [2007](#), blue shaded area in Figure 4). The tension between simulations and observations can be alleviated if we assume that a significant percentage of the accreted stellar mass ends up in the cluster’s ICL rather than in the Brightest Cluster Galaxy (BCG) (between 30–80%, Conroy et al. [2007](#); Laporte et al. [2013](#);

Contini et al. [2018](#)). This brings the predictions of the models into better agreement with the observations (purple area in [Figure 13](#)).

Figure 13: Mass growth rate of the BCG with redshift. Green dots are observations from: Whiley et al. (2008); Collins et al. (2009); Stott et al. (2010); Lidman et al. (2012); Lin et al. (2013); Oliva-Altamirano et al. (2014); Burke et al. (2015); Bellstedt et al. (2016); Zhang et al. (2016). The blue and purple shaded areas are simulations from de Lucia & Blaizot (2007) and Contini et al. (2018), respectively (figure from Montes [2019](#)).

The relative importance of the mechanisms responsible for the ICL will likely vary during the evolution history of the cluster and, possibly, within different regions of the cluster. A useful tool to determine the properties of the ICL is the study of its stellar populations. In fact, the ages and metallicities of the ICL population reflect the properties of the progenitor galaxies from which the stars got stripped. For example, Contini et al. (2014) predicted that the bulk of the ICL light is stripped from the most massive ($M^* \sim 10^{10} - 10^{11} M_{\odot}$) galaxies as they fall into the cluster core (see also Rudick et al. 2011; Cooper et al. 2013). If this is the case, the ICL should exhibit a mean metallicity like in the outer regions of these massive satellites. Additionally, the age of the ICL stellar populations should give us an upper limit on when the formation of the ICL took place. This is because we do not expect any star formation in the ICL component after their stars have been stripped from their progenitor objects. In this sense, knowing the age and metallicity of the ICL of the clusters allow us to infer how (and when) the assembly history of these clusters was, ranging from the shredding of dwarf galaxies (Purcell et al. 2007; Contini et al. 2014), to violent mergers with the central galaxies of the cluster (Murante et al. 2007; Conroy et al. 2007), or in situ formation (Puchwein et al. 2010).

Studies of ICL colors show clear radial gradients (Iodice et al. 2017; Mihos et al. 2017; DeMaio et al. 2015, 2018) indicating radial variations in metallicity and, in some cases, age. These gradients point to tidal stripping of massive satellites as the dominant process of ICL formation. In fact, the metallicities found in the ICL region indicate that the progenitors of the unbound stars are the outskirts of galaxies of masses around $3 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$. Spectroscopic studies of stellar populations in ICL (Coccatto et al. 2010; Melnick et al. 2012; Edwards et al. 2016) offer contradictory results. Melnick et al. (2012) found that the ICL is dominated by old, metal rich stars (75%) while Coccatto et al. (2011), using Lick indices, found that 100% of the ICL stars in the Hydra-I cluster were old and metal poor. Most spectroscopic studies have used long slit

spectroscopy placed in two or three directions (see Figure 14 from the positions in Toledo et al. [2011](#)) and then stack the light to increase the signal-to-noise ratio.

Furthermore, the same process that contribute to remove material from galaxies and make the ICL (harassment, tidal interactions, mergers), affect both, the stellar and gas content of galaxies, and can strongly change their morphology (Aguerre et al. [2004](#), [2005](#); Lisker et al. [2006](#); Méndez-Abreu et al. [2010](#); Aguerri [2016](#)), kinematics (Pedraz et al. [2002](#); Geha et al. [2003](#); Toloba et al. [2009](#)), and stellar content (Haines et al. [2006](#); Smith et al. [2009](#)) of galaxies on time-scales smaller than a few Gyr (Montes & Trujillo [2014](#), [2018](#)). Therefore, the results from the ICL need to be explained with a single scenario that ought to also explain the star formation histories of galaxies and their chemical abundances. This search for consistency is one of the characteristics that have defined the design of CATARSIS.

Studying this component is extremely challenging to probe due to its very low surface brightness ($\mu_V \gtrsim 26$ mag/arcsec², e.g., Mihos et al. [2005](#); Zibetti et al. [2005](#); Rudick et al. [2010](#)). Due to its extended nature in the sky, sky subtraction is particularly difficult as it requires large fields of view to accurately determine the sky background without contamination from the ICL itself, even at intermediate redshifts. In addition, the ICL is normally contaminated by foreground and background (in projection) galaxies. Moreover, the separation between the ICL and the outer region of the brightest central galaxies is an ill-defined problem (e.g., Gonzalez et al. [2005](#); Krick & Bernstein [2007](#); Rudick et al. [2011](#); Jimenez-Teja & Dupke [2016](#)).

TARSIS is an ideal instrument to study the stellar populations of ICL. First, the amount of ICL observed will be much larger than with any other instrument before and the 2D spectroscopy will make sky subtraction and decontamination from galaxy members much easier. On top of that, the observational strategy proposed for CATARSIS implies that the final blue arm spectra are obtained as an average of spectra in 3 different CCDs using a total of 15 individual exposures per pointing. This results in a very uniform background over the whole field of view.

Figure 14: Approximate positions of the slits where the various components of the ICL by Toledo et al. (2011) and the integrated spectra.

A large FoV is key for the success of this science case as it will allow to increase the low signal of this component. In this case it would be also important to perform the observations in the "Staring mode" so to obtain a highly homogeneous background. A $R=1000$ spectral resolution will allow a better separation of contaminants.

2.7 Galaxies' velocity dispersion function

A generic prediction of the Λ CDM cosmology is that the properties of the galaxy population must be closely related to that of the halo population. If the cosmological density field is Gaussian and if the power of density perturbations extends to large scales, as is the case in the current CDM cosmogony, halo properties are expected to be correlated to some degree with the LSS, and so the properties of the galaxy population are also expected to change with large-scale environment. However, numerical simulations indicate that a strong correlation with the large-scale environment exists only for halo mass; all other important halo properties are at most weakly correlated with the large-scale environment at any given time (e.g., Lemson & Kauffmann 1999). This result implies that the environmental dependence of the galaxy population is mainly due to the change in the halo mass function with large-scale environment. We can therefore hope to understand the environmental dependence of the galaxy population by understanding how galaxies occupy DM haloes of different masses.

The luminosity function has long been used to link galaxies to their DM subhalos (e.g., Klypin et al. 1999; Vale & Ostriker 2004; Yang et al. 2008) and many studies have shown that the shapes vary with environment (e.g., Hwang et al. 2012; Calvi et al. 2013; Vulcani et al. 2013; Davidzon et al. 2016; Papovich et al. 2018). However, it is difficult to establish the origin of this without any other information.

For the quiescent galaxy population, the stellar velocity dispersion (σ) function complements the luminosity and stellar-mass functions (e.g., Sheth et al. [2003](#); Chae [2010](#)). The stellar velocity dispersion of a quiescent galaxy is a proxy for the DM halo dispersion (Wake et al. [2012](#); Bogdan & Goulding [2015](#); Zahid et al. [2016](#), [2018](#)) and is insensitive to the complex physics of the evolving stellar population and to minor mergers. Measuring the stellar velocity dispersions is straightforward compared to untangling the systematic errors in dense cluster photometry that affect both the luminosity and stellar-mass measurements, and offers a more direct comparison with numerical simulations, as it is less dependent on the complicated baryonic physics that are quite sensitive to the details of the sub-grid recipes. The comparison between the luminosity and velocity dispersion function will allow to test these predictions.

The velocity dispersion function has been measured for just a few clusters (Sohn et al. [2017](#), [2020](#)). The results indicate that the velocity dispersion function of more massive cluster tends to have a steeper slope for $\log [\sigma \text{ (km s}^{-1}\text{)}] > 2.2$. In other words, more massive clusters tend to have a smaller fraction of galaxies with large σ than less massive clusters. However, a comprehensive interpretation of the observed cluster velocity dispersion function is challenging. A broad set of observations is required to develop a complete picture given the complex theoretical landscape. Issues range from the selection of the galaxies in the cluster to the inclusion of galaxy radii, galaxy shapes, the ICL, the distribution of massive cluster members, the role of AGN, and possibly spatially-resolved spectroscopy of the cluster members. CATARSIS is the ideal instrument to alleviate many of these issues. As we do not need to pre-select our galaxies, our spectra is not limited to a given aperture, so we can analyze the ICL light and also the galaxy shapes and check the effect that each of them have on the final result, taking a huge step in our understanding of the halo-occupation function, and also putting constrains on the baryonic physics needed to reproduce both functions.

At the redshift range of the CATARSIS clusters, the wavelength range where the spectral resolution of the spectrograph is higher covers the region of the Mgb triplet. Using the most pessimistic numbers (that are above the requirements of the instrument), we will be able to measure velocity dispersions as low as ~ 60 km/s for galaxies with $m_{r,AB} < 19$ mag and ~ 105 km/s for galaxies up to $m_{r,AB} = 21$ mag (Pedraz et al. [2002](#)) using this spectral region. The large FoV is key to extend the analysis in order to have enough statistics.

3. EVOLUTION OF GALAXIES IN CLUSTERS

It has long been known that in the local universe the mix of morphological types differs in different galactic environments with ellipticals and S0's dominating in the densest clusters and spirals dominating the field population (Hubble & Humason [1931](#)). This so-called density-morphology relation has been quantified by Oemler ([1974](#)) and Dressler ([1980](#)) and is found to extend over five orders of magnitude in space density (Postman and Geller [1984](#)). In addition, it has been shown that both the morphological mix and the SFR strongly evolve with redshift (Poggianti et al. [1999](#); Dressler et al. [1997](#); Fasano et al. [2000](#)) with the fraction of spiral galaxies and the star formation going up at increasing redshift while the fraction of S0's goes down.

In principle, this evolution can be explained if star-forming galaxies (SFGs) are continuously entering the cluster environment where different processes are capable of turning them into passively-evolving systems (Haines et al. [2007](#)): gravitational interactions with the potential well

of nearby galaxies or the cluster itself (harassment), removal and thermal heating of the interstellar medium of the galaxies by the interaction with the intra-cluster medium or ram-pressure stripping (Quilis et al. [2000](#); Bekki [2009](#); Kawata & Mulchaey [2008](#)), or the removal of hot gas reservoirs from galaxy halos (strangulation, Kawata & Mulchaey [2008](#)). These mechanisms shape the galaxy evolution in different timescales (from 100 Myr to 1 Gyr), and with different efficiency depending on the properties of both, galaxies and clusters, and the circumstances under which infall takes place (Boselli & Gavazzi [2006](#); Berrier et al. [2009](#)).

In addition to the role of the environment, it has been clearly demonstrated that the mass of the galaxy is the other key parameter that regulates the evolution and the SFH (see, e.g., Sánchez-Blázquez et al. [2006](#); Peng et al. [2010](#); Greene et al. [2019](#)). Clusters host the most massive galaxies in the Universe, and the different mass distribution can also be responsible of the observed differences.

Despite the advances that have been made in the last decades to understand galaxy evolution, the link between mass assembly and star formation in galaxies and its relationship with intrinsic properties (such as galaxy mass), or environment (such as parent halo mass) still remains an open question. The debate remains as if this is due to the different initial conditions (nature), or if it is due to the interaction with the environment (nurture) and affects both, observational and theoretical work.

Part of the problem is that environment, usually defined as the excess number of galaxies seen in projection, fails to incorporate the intrinsic dynamics of the different structures that define the cosmic web (see, e.g., Aguerri et al. [2018](#); Roberts & Parker [2017](#)) or the thermodynamical conditions of the intracluster medium (ICM) which is essential to understand what the impact of interactions is between this medium and galaxies. Furthermore, clusters can interact with each other, which can affect the galaxies living in them. Mergers of galaxy clusters produce the largest energy release in the Universe after the big bang itself, with energies up to orders of 10^{63} erg (e.g., Feretti et al. [2002](#)), and the drivers of star formation and black hole activity in cluster galaxies seem to be closely linked to the merger history of the host cluster and its associated filaments and infalling groups, opening a new window into how galaxies evolve.

3.1 Transformations of galaxies in clusters

The various mechanisms that can transform galaxies when they fall into a cluster act on different timescales, ranging from 100 Myr to 1 Gyr. Therefore, the identification of the most influential ones requires an accurate reconstruction of the SFH of galaxies, especially in this time range, and relate it with the time since it was accreted by the cluster.

A useful tool to investigate the second is the projected phase-space diagram which combines the cluster-centric velocities and radii in one plot (see Smith et al. [2015](#); Jaffé et al. [2015](#); Rhee et al. [2017](#); Owers et al. [2019](#), and references therein). Galaxies that are infalling for the first time into the cluster are found at projected distances beyond the virial radius with lower velocities than galaxies that are passing close to the pericenter, which are close to the cluster center (Rhee et al. [2017](#)). The galaxies that fell into the cluster several Gyr ago are in the regions of lower relative velocities (see Figure 15).

Despite the known projection effects, cosmological simulations have shown that it is possible to separate the oldest from the most recently accreted cluster members in this diagram. Galaxies with intermediate time-since-infall (including backplash galaxies¹) are harder to distinguish, as they overlap in phase-space with both the virialized and the recent infall galaxies (Oman, Hudson & Behroozi [2013](#); Jaffé et al. [2015](#); Rhee et al. [2017](#)). However, Yoon et al. ([2017](#)) recently showed that it is possible to identify the backplash population combining the phase-space location of cluster galaxies with detailed HI observations, which they used as a proxy for the galaxy's stripping stage and thus time since infall.

For clusters with significant substructure it should be noted that the intensity of ram-pressure can be enhanced at places and inhomogeneous across the cluster and that the orbits (and thus velocities) of infalling galaxies can also be altered (Owers et al. [2012](#); Vijayaraghavan & Ricker [2013](#); Jaffé et al. [2016](#); McPartland et al. [2016](#)). Therefore, the analysis of the substructure will need to be considered.

Figure 15: Stacked caustic profile of the 30 most massive clusters in the Millenium cosmological simulation as they would be observed at $z = 0.21$. Each point indicates a galaxy from the Bower et al. ([2006](#)) semi-analytic models, colored according to when it was accreted into the cluster, those being accreted earliest being indicated by red symbols. Here, accretion epoch is defined as the redshift when the galaxy passes within r_{500} for the first time. Galaxies yet to pass through R_{500} by $z = 0.21$ are indicated in blue and dominate at large cluster-centric radii and along the caustics. Figure from Haines et al. ([2012](#)).

3.1.1 Measuring star formation histories in CATARSIS

The UV has the highest sensitivity of any spectral region to stellar temperature and metal abundance, implying that it is especially valuable as a mean of characterizing stellar populations, current star formation rates (SFRs), and SFHs. Stars with surface temperatures above $\sim 10,000$ K (e.g., main-sequence stars with masses $\gtrsim 3 M_{\odot}$) are brighter in the UV than at longer wavelengths (Fanelli et al. [1992](#)). Consequently, UV spectroscopy permits direct detection of the massive stars responsible for most ionization, photo-dissociation, kinetic energy input, and element synthesis.

¹ Note that in the literature while those cluster galaxies that have passed through their host halo and are outside the virial radius are called back-*splash* galaxies, the radius within which most of them are located is commonly called *splash-back* radius (the other way around; see, e.g., O'Neil et al. [2023](#)).

The timescales which can be probed by observations of the 2850-3400 Å continuum range from less than 10 Myr to ≥ 1 Gyr. This critical interval cannot be obtained using only the optical region (3400-9000 Å), which is influenced by the SFH on longer timescales (more than a few Gyr). To illustrate this, **Figure 16** shows the predicted UV-IR spectral energy distributions of stellar populations over timescales up to 3 Gyr. The strong time evolution of the UV compared to longer wavelengths is the reason for its utility in determining population ages. The sensitivity of the UV to stellar properties extends even to the cool $\approx 1 M_{\odot}$ stars near the main-sequence turnoff in the oldest model shown in this figure. These solar-type stars dominate the mid-UV (2000-3400 Å) light in this model, in which both chemical composition and age influence the output spectrum. Indeed, the concentration of strong metallic absorption features is responsible for much of the short-wavelength structure seen this model.

Furthermore, the high luminosity of young stars in this range makes possible to detect very small amounts of recent star formation on top of a much older component, giving us the opportunity to derive detailed SFHs. To illustrate this, we show we compare in Figure 17 the spectrum of a 10 Gyr-old simple stellar population (SSP) and the spectrum of the same population with a very small contribution 0.01% in mass of a 63 Myr old component. This small contribution of a young population barely changes the optical spectrum, but it is clearly visible below 3000 Å.

Figure 16: Predicted Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) for four Simple Stellar Population (SSP) models with four different ages as indicated in the figure.

The use of full spectral fitting techniques (e.g., Ocvirk et al. [2006](#); Sánchez-Blázquez et al. [2011](#)) in combination with the recently extended stellar population models E-MILES (Vazdekis et al. [2017](#)) are extremely useful tools to reconstruct with exquisite detail the star formation history of galaxies. The rest-frame wavelength coverage of CATARSIS (2780–6610 Å) at $z = 0.15$ and (2500–5940 Å) at $z = 0.28$ will allow to detect residual star formation at the 1% level in mass in spectra with a $S/N \sim 10$ at 2750 Å, similar to the expected signal in CATARSIS for a galaxy with $r = 20-21$ mag. Salvador-Rusiñol ([2019](#)) was able to detect, using stacked spectra from the BOSS survey, fractions of 0.5% of young population in the last 2 Gyr with spectra of similar quality.

Figure 17: Top: UV-optical SED of two stellar populations, one Simple Stellar Population (SSP) of 10 Gyr (in black) and one SSP with a 0.01% (in mass) young burst (63 Myr-old, in red). Bottom: Ratio between the two models. Note that only in the UV range the two spectra show significant differences.

CATARSIS will allow measuring the whole sequence of galaxy transformations, relating them to the epoch of accretion into the cluster and to thermodynamical conditions of the ICM gas, and the substructure of the cluster. We will measure detailed SFH that will allow to study very low levels of star formation and, therefore, trace the quenching processes over longer periods of time than $H\alpha$ SFR measurements, relating it with the properties of the cluster.

To derive detailed SFH we need to obtain spectra in the rest-frame region 280-320 nm, as this region is extremely sensitive to the presence of young stars. Studies of stellar populations using the optical part of the spectra require signal-to-noise (S/N) per angstrom above 30 to minimize the effects of the age-metallicity degeneracy. However, the information contained in the NUV part of the spectra allows relaxing this condition. This is illustrated in Figure 18 (Costantin et al. 2019), that shows the probability distribution function of the ages derived with optical and optical+NUV line-strength indices in two spectra with different SFH and S/N. It is clear that when NUV indices are used, unbiased ages can be measured in spectra with $S/N = 10$, which we will be able to obtain in the spectrum of galaxies with small fractions of young stars, due to the dramatic increase in the flux that we expect at these wavelengths (see Figure 17).

Figure 18: Examples of Probability Distribution Functions (PDFs) of r -magnitude weighted mean age for a simulated galaxy with a SFH that includes a small fraction of young population. PDFs retrieved using only optical indices are in red and those obtained with both ultraviolet and optical indices in blue. The blue shaded region represents the confidence interval corresponding to the 16-84 per cent percentile range of the PDF. The solid green line corresponds to the true value, $\langle \text{age} \rangle_{r\text{-mag}} = 4.44$ Gyr, and the dashed vertical red (blue) line indicates the median value of the corresponding distribution.

3.1.2 The importance of 2D-spectroscopy

There is mounting evidence that ram-pressure stripping (RPS) is one of the most effective mechanisms quenching galaxies in clusters. Simulations show that RPS can effectively remove cold gas from galaxies, and in some cases temporarily enhance the star-formation activity before quenching it completely (see, e.g., Steinhauser, Schindler & Springel [2016](#), and references therein). Evidence supporting RPS comes from observations of neutral gas (HI) (Haynes, Giovanelli & Chincarini [1984](#); Cayatte et al. [1990](#); Chung et al. [2009](#); Vollmer et al. [2001](#); Jaffé et al. [2015](#)) showing cold gas in the process of being stripped from the galaxy (see Figure 19).

In some cases, stars are formed in the stripped gas (Kenney & Koopmann [1999](#); Kenney et al. [2014](#)), and can thus be identified from UV or optical images. The most striking examples of stripped galaxies with new stars tracing the stripped tails are the so-called “Jellyfish” galaxies. Estimates based on small blind H α surveys of Coma and A1367 indicate that the fraction of cluster late-type galaxies with these features is close to 40% (Boselli & Gavazzi [2014](#)).

RPS is inversely proportional to radius of the cluster, as both the ICM density and the free-fall velocity increase as a galaxy approaches the cluster centre. The second term, however, is the binding energy of the galaxy, that decrease at increasing radius. This is evident in Figure 19, showing that the gas is being removed from outside-in.

Figure 19: False-color SDSS images of galaxies falling into the Virgo cluster. The HI emission (coming from the VIVA survey; Chung et al. 2009) is indicated with the white contours, showing the neutral gas of the galaxy is being stripped from outside-in (from Wong et al. 2014).

If we limit our analysis to the central apertures, we will be missing the important effects of RPS during a large period of the crossing time, when the density is not high enough to remove the gas for the galaxy center. The spatial resolution of CATARSIS will allow us to resolve regions between 5 kpc and 7.5 kpc at $z = 0.15$ and 0.25 respectively, enough to study the effects of this process on galaxy properties from much earlier. Furthermore, a 2D analysis will give important insight into the stellar and gas kinematics in these highly disturbed galaxies (e.g. Fumagalli et al. 2014; Bellhouse et al. 2017; Kalita & Ebeling 2019), detect the presence of star formation induced by the hot gas pressure, and the fraction of new stars that form outside the galaxy.

3.2 Chemical evolution in clusters and the star formation history of galaxies

Theoretical models of chemical evolution, coupled with state-of-the-art galaxy evolution models will also play an increasingly important role. The complexity and non-linearity of the processes driving the chemistry at high redshift require better and more accurate numerical simulations.

From the effect of stellar feedback, the initial mass function (IMF), and detailed nucleosynthesis to the birth and growth of supermassive black holes (SMBHs), observations need to guide these theoretical predictions.

Clusters of galaxies are unique laboratories for the study of the nucleosynthesis and chemical enrichment of the Universe as their deep gravitational potential wells keep all the metals produced by the stellar populations of the member galaxies within the cluster, making them the closer the closed-box model approximation. The dominant fraction of these metals reside within the hot ICM. The chemical abundances measured in the intra-cluster plasma thus provide us with a “fossil” record of the integral yield of all the different stars (releasing metals in supernova explosions and winds) that have left their specific abundance patterns in the gas prior and during cluster evolution. The detection of an overabundance of α -elements with ASCA suggests that the metals in the ICM might come mainly from Type II SNe (Loewenstein & Mushotzky 1996; Mushotzky et al. 1996). Thus, one of the possible mechanisms for the metal enrichment of the ICM is a wind from proto-galaxies driven by Type II SNe explosions in their early evolutionary phase (*aka* early galactic wind). In a hierarchical universe, it has been shown that the epoch of galaxy formation is earlier than that of cluster formation, that is it, in the protocluster.

Some simple theoretical attempts of chemical and population synthesis modelling failed to simultaneously match the constraints on ICM metallicity and on the stellar mass-to-light ratios (Renzini & Andreon 2014; Loewenstein 2013; Ghizzardi et al. 2021). These authors claimed that the iron yield in the largest clusters ($M_{500,\text{crit}} > 10^{14} M_{\odot}$) must be a few times the solar value. Two main solutions have been suggested, one is a time-dependent IMF and the other is related to variations in the Type-Ia SNe yields. However, either solution should explain not only the mass distribution of elliptical galaxies, but also their detailed chemical abundances.

If the ICM enrichment is due to strong winds in protocluster galaxies with very high SFR, we will expect that bright elliptical galaxies in the center of clusters have a high Mg/Fe. Indeed, elliptical galaxies in the center of clusters show a uniform age and a [Mg/Fe] that increases with galaxy mass (e.g., Kuntschner et al. 1998, Sánchez-Blázquez et al. 2006). This relation seems to be the same independent of the cluster mass or X-ray luminosity (Carretero et al. 2004). Contrary to this, CN in elliptical galaxies have also shown that galaxies with the same mass (and [Mg/Fe]) show a much more prominent CN feature in X-ray luminous clusters, indicating that the SFHs were not the same for galaxies in all clusters (Figure 20). As C and N are mainly release by intermediate-mass stars, this has been interpreted as the consequence of slightly more extended SFHs in less massive clusters. This fine-tuned SFH would have been long enough for the Type II SNe to explode, so their products could be incorporated in the next generation of stars but, in the most massive clusters, it was stopped before intermediate mass stars had time to reach the AGB. If this happened at the proto-cluster stage, then the mechanism that caused it must be related with its present-day cluster mass.

For example, a time-dependent IMF whereby a strongly star-forming system starts with a top-heavy IMF, followed by a later phase where a large amount of gas is locked into low-mass stars (Vazdekis et al. 1996, 1997; Davé 2008) could explain the observed abundances. However, this scenario produces high values of [Mg/Fe], chemical enrichment properties, X-ray binary fractions, as well as the IMF signatures in the spectra of early-type galaxies (ETGs, Weidner et

al. 2013; Ferreras et al. 2015), that should be examined in detail. If we invoke variations in the SNIa yields to explain the Fe abundance in the ICM, they should also be compatible with the chemical abundance ratios of ETGs in clusters.

Figure 20: Cluster X-ray luminosity vs. overabundance values of $[ZCN/ZFe]$ (top), $[ZMg/ZFe]$ (middle) and $[ZMg/ZCN]$ (bottom). Circles, squares, and triangles indicate clusters with richness classes of 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Each point corresponds to one individual cluster and represents the interpolated abundance ratio for $\sigma = 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The Spearman rank-order correlation coefficients and its significance values are written in top and bottom panels (from Carretero et al. 2004).

X-ray observations of galaxy clusters show that the ICM contains large amounts of heavy elements, such as O, Ne, Mg, Si, S, Ar, Ca, and Fe (e.g., Werner et al. 2008). The constant ratios of abundances of several of these elements found throughout the Virgo cluster (Simionescu et al. 2015) as well as in the radial profiles of 44 clusters observed out to intermediate radii with XMM-Newton (Mernier et al. 2017) indicate that, during the early period of metal enrichment, the products of core-collapse and Type Ia SNe were well mixed. The estimated ratio between the number of Type Ia SNe and the total number of SNe enriching the ICM is about 15–20%, percentage that will need to be consistent with the stellar chemical abundances in galaxies, that we will measure with CATARSIS. A consistent chemical evolution model that incorporates but stellar and hot-gas components should put strong constrains on the early epoch of protocluster formation and it will allow to probe or discard the need for a time changing IMF.

3.2.1 Stellar and interstellar medium chemical abundances

In the local universe, the chemistry of galaxies is generally investigated by targeting two distinct types of galaxies. The simplicity and high-surface brightness of massive, quiescent galaxies makes them ideal candidates for studying stellar absorption features, especially in their central regions. Consequently, they are traditional benchmarks for stellar population modelling and the study of the stellar abundances in external galaxies. The chemistry of the ISM, on the other hand, is studied in star-forming galaxies, where the gas is excited in HII regions by the presence of massive stars. This dichotomy has led also to contradictory results and to significant gaps in our

understanding of the chemical evolution of galaxies. The wavelength range covered by CATARSIS will allow the measurement of two chemical elements, Nitrogen and Magnesium in both components: the stars and the nebular gas. Stellar Nitrogen abundances can be obtained from the NH3375 index defined by Servén (2010), while Mg can be obtained from Mg2800, Mg2852, Mg3334 and also from Mgb (see Figure 21). Abundances of the Nitrogen ions in the warm gas can be obtained from [NII]6584Å while the presence of MgII2800 emission will give us access to the abundance of this ion. As the NH3375 line will be dominated by the youngest component, the comparison with the abundance of NII can be used to calibrate the ionization corrections for integrated spectra, when individual HII regions cannot be resolved, for different metallicities and SFRs. These corrections are a very important source of uncertainty in measurements of nebular abundances, but they are difficult to constrain observationally, especially in external galaxies. The comparison of nebular and stellar Mg or the nebular O will be interesting to study the destruction of dust by the hot ICM.

Figure 21: Sketch of the most prominent absorption features in the NUV: Mg II 2800 Å, the Fe I 3000 Å which trace four neutral magnesium lines (2966.90; 2984.73; 2999.81 and 3021.37 Å), the two iron FeII features at 2402 and 2609 Å and MgI at 2852 Å.

We also be able to test common interpretations of nebular line ratios. According to theoretical models, the gas-phase N/O abundance ratio in galaxies is strongly influenced by the SFH of galaxies (e.g., Henry et al. 2000; Mollá et al. 2006; Vincenzo & Kobayashi 2018). Therefore, the N/O–O/H diagram (for individual star forming complexes and also for global average values for integrated galaxy spectra) has been suggested as an alternative SFH chemical abundance diagnostic of galaxies (e.g., Vincenzo et al. 2016; Chiappini, Matteucci & Ballero 2005; Mollá et al. 2006). In the nebular component, The N/O abundance ratio will be derived from the ratio of the [NII]λ6584Å and [OII]λλ3726,3729Å emission lines, via the N2O2 parameter (Pérez-Montero & Contini 2009), while the gas-phase O/H chemical abundance can be derived from a number of strong emission-lines present in the spectral range (namely [OII]λλ3726,3729Å, Hβ, [OIII]λ5007Å, Hα, [NII]λ6584Å). The comparison of N/O with the SFH derived with a full spectral fitting (see previous section) will tell us if the first is, indeed, an alternative to measure the second.

The CATARSIS survey will offer an excellent data sample to test chemical evolution models' predictions using both ionized gas and stellar abundances. The TARSIS wavelength range contains a plethora of absorption and emission lines that, combined with the derived SFHs, will give us new information to calibrate and interpret commonly used features to measure chemical abundances.

3.2.1.1 *Evolution of the IMF*

As we mentioned above, a possible solution to reconcile the chemical abundances in hot halos in clusters with the mass-to-light ratios of galaxies is to use a top-heavy IMF. This is also a condition for semi-analytical models of galaxy formation and chemodynamical simulations to reproduce the relation between the stellar [Mg/Fe] and velocity dispersion observed in elliptical galaxies (Yates et al. [2013](#); Arrigoni et al. [2010](#)).

However, in the last few years, improved technology and population synthesis modelling have allowed to use spectral line-strength indices that are sensitive to the giant vs. dwarf stellar ratio as a discriminant of the IMF in passive populations. Early results (Cenarro et al. [2003](#); van Dokkum & Conry [2010](#)), later confirmed with independent data and analysis (e.g., Ferreras et al. [2013](#); La Barbera et al. [2013](#)) indicate the opposite, a bottom-heavy IMF in elliptical galaxies. These results were supported by dynamical constraints, produced at around the same time but based on kinematic studies of IFU data of nearby galaxies (Cappellari et al. [2012](#), [2013](#)), that revealed high values of the stellar mass-to-light ratios with respect to the expectations from a standard, Milky Way-type IMF). Gravitational lensing over galaxy scales provides a third, independent probe of the bottom-heavy IMF in massive early-type galaxies (Treu et al. [2010](#); Smith & Lucey [2013](#)).

A way to solve this problem is by invoking a time-dependent IMF whereby a strongly star-forming system starts with a top-heavy IMF, followed by a later phase where a large amount of gas is locked into low-mass stars (Vazdekis et al. [1996](#), [1997](#); Davé [2008](#)). This scenario produces chemical enrichment properties, X-ray binary fractions, as well as the IMF signatures found in massive ETGs (Weidner et al. [2013](#); Ferreras et al. [2015](#)), although it is admittedly contrived.

The relation between SFR and IMF was explored by Hoversten & Glazebrook ([2008](#)) in a sample of star forming galaxies using a combination of H α EW and g-r color (see Figure 22). They found that low SFR galaxies lie below models with a Salpeter IMF ($\alpha = -2.35$), towards the bottom track for $\alpha = -3.0$. In contrast, those with high SFR lie towards the top-heavy model with $\alpha = -2.0$.

Figure 22: Galaxies from the GAMA survey with three different SFR. The evolutionary tracks predicted by PEGASE (solid) and maraston (dashed) for three IMF (-3, -2.35 and -2, top to bottom) are indicated.

On the other hand, a correlation between the IMF and the metal content has been found in elliptical galaxies, both globally and as a function of radius. To disentangle between a strong star formation and metallicity is difficult as one goes usually associated to the other at a given time.

Thanks to the rest-frame NUV observations of CATARSIS, we can contribute to shed some light to this problem in an independent way. The FeI300 spectral index, with values that are nearly twice for dwarf stars than for super-giants, is a strong feature, especially in star-forming galaxies. Besides, it has the advantage that is not affected by dust reddening and it is not contaminated by older populations. Furthermore, the cluster environment may give us the possibility of finding galaxies with similar SFR and different metallicities, or vice-versa, for example by comparing galaxies in merging clusters with others that are just infalling into the cluster.

4. BEHIND THE CLUSTERS

Observations of deep extragalactic fields performed with MUSE (HDFS, Bacon et al. 2015; UDF, Bacon et al. 2017; CDFS, Urrutia et al. 2019; MUDF, Lusso et al. 2019) have demonstrated how a wide-field optical IFU is a game-changer for the study of distant galaxies. It provides a comprehensive spectroscopic view of the sky, i.e., high-quality spectra for all sources in the FoV with no prior selection. This approach has produced an order of magnitude increase in the number of spectroscopic redshifts measured in these deep fields (Herenz et al. 2017; Inami et al. 2017; Brinchmann et al. 2017), thereby revealing systematically groups and associations of galaxies that would never have been targeted for spectroscopic follow-up otherwise (e.g., Ventou et al. 2017).

Our deep exposures will serendipitously observe a large variety of different objects at high redshifts, and thanks to its blue coverage, the current MUSE redshift desert ($z = [1.5 - 3]$, corresponding to the redshift of [O II] $\lambda\lambda 3726, 3729\text{\AA}$ emitters at the red end and of Lyman Alpha Emitters –LAEs– at the blue end) will be largely filled down to $z = 1.63$ by CATARSIS. Among other things, this will allow us to better characterize the nature Damped Lyman Alpha systems, [OII], HeII or Ly α emitters. We will be able to observe Ly α and MgII emission at the same time in objects between $1.63 < z < 1.9$, which will be a giant step to understand the resonance nature of both lines and to quantify the Ly α escape fraction. Furthermore, our detection limit will allow the study the emission of the intergalactic medium and, therefore, to understand better the physics

of gas inflows and outflows in galaxies. CATARSIS will provide new ways of exploring the physics associated to high-redshift objects allowing the same study to be done at much lower redshifts. Although these projects are normally carried out in large aperture telescopes, the large field of view, the much smaller cosmic dimming, and the efficiency of TARSIS make this project highly competitive.

Using the Ultra-Fast Image Generator (UFug) for wide astronomy surveys (Berge et al. [2013](#)) and a limiting magnitude of $r = 22$ mag, we calculate that the number of galaxies observed serendipitously will be 8000 to 9000 per square degree. This adds up to a total of 12000-15300 spectra at the end of the survey. The detection of galaxies with strong emission lines will more than triple this number.

4.1 The Lyman-alpha transition

With a vacuum rest-frame wavelength of 1215.67 \AA , the Lyman- α ($\text{Ly}\alpha$) recombination line ($n = 2 \rightarrow n = 1$) is intrinsically the strongest emission line in the rest-frame UV and optical (e.g., Partridge & Peebles [1967](#); Pritchett [1994](#)). $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission from stellar populations and AGN is a powerful diagnostic of high-redshift objects, enabling the effective identification and spectroscopic confirmation of these sources (Bromm & Yoshida [2011](#); Finkelstein [2016](#)).

The blue wavelength coverage of CATARSIS will allow the detection of LAEs at redshifts in the range $1.63 < z < 3$, which coincides with the rise and fall of the SFR density in the Universe (i.e. the "Cosmic Noon"). The spectral resolution of CATARSIS will allow to study the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ profile containing important information about the radiative transfer on the clouds and about the escape of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ photons, which is of vital importance to understand the epoch of reionization. CATARSIS observations will also detect the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission of the circumgalactic medium (CGM; Steidel et al. [2011](#); Hayes et al. [2013](#); Momose et al. [2016](#); Leclercq et al. [2017](#); Erb et al. [2018](#)) which will allow studying the gas accretion processes into the galaxies.

4.1.1 The physics of the Lyman-alpha transition

Due to the complex physics of the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ radiative transfer process, it has proven difficult to interpret the results from theoretical models and observational data (Dijkstra [2014](#)) despite the fact that understanding the physics of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ escape has major implications.

$\text{Ly}\alpha$ equivalent width ($W_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$) and the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ escape fraction ($f_{\text{esc}}^{\text{Ly}\alpha}$) are higher ($W_{\text{Ly}\alpha} \gtrsim 20 \text{ \AA}$ and $f_{\text{esc}}^{\text{Ly}\alpha} \gtrsim 10\%$) in galaxies that represent the less massive and younger end of the distribution of galaxies in the local universe. This relates to various properties, such as the fact that $\text{Ly}\alpha$ -emitting galaxies have lower metal abundances (median value of $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) \sim 8.1$) and dust reddening. However, the presence of galactic outflows/winds is also vital to *Doppler shift* the $\text{Ly}\alpha$ line out of resonance with the atomic gas, as high $W_{\text{Ly}\alpha}$ is found only among galaxies with winds faster than $\sim 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In fact, self-consistently incorporating non-ionizing continuum and other hydrogen, nebular, and metal absorption lines into $\text{Ly}\alpha$ studies helps to disentangle certain radiative transfer effects that are either amplified or suppressed by resonant scattering. For example, different types of line and continuum radiation may have unique spatial, spectral, and angular escape or absorption features that help to determine the relative importance of turbulent ISM porosity compared to smoother spherical and disc-like density gradients. This is also significant because ionizing radiation and stellar feedback act to clear low-column density

channels that facilitate the escape of Ly α photons as suggested by several theoretical works (e.g., Yajima et al. 2014; Dijkstra et al. 2016; Kimm et al. 2019; Kakiichi & Gronke 2021; Mauerhofer et al. 2021) and observational studies (e.g., Nakajima & Ouchi 2014; Henry et al. 2015; Chisholm et al. 2018; Gazagnes et al. 2020; Jaskot et al. 2019).

The spectral resolution of CATARSIS will be enough to resolve the double peak of the Ly α emission and therefore, study the escape fraction in relation to both the dynamics and the metallicity of the cloud (see Section 4.1.4). This is easily seen in Figure 23; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, that shows the Ly α profile of a LAE at $z = 1.88$ observed with the LRIS (Oke et al. 1995) spectrograph with a *grism* that gives an average resolution of FWHM $\sim 4.0 \text{ \AA}$ (275 km s^{-1}), very similar to what we will achieve in CATARSIS (from Berg et al. 2018).

Figure 23: Velocity profile of the double-peaked Ly α emission in SL2S0217, a LAE at $z = 1.8$. The overall profile is reasonably well fit using two Gaussians (blue lines). Interestingly, the blue component is stronger than the red one and has a slightly larger velocity width. The Ly α peak separation is relatively small, but can be resolved with observations made with a spectral resolution FWHM = 4 \AA (from Berg et al. 2008).

4.1.2 Lyman-alpha emitters

Already more than 50 years ago, the Ly α emission line of hydrogen was predicted to be a superb tracer for galaxy formation and evolution studies in the high redshift universe (Partridge & Peebles 1967). Meanwhile the study of LAEs has provided a route to identify low-mass galaxies at high redshifts that possibly constitute the progenitors of present-day L* galaxies such as the Milky Way (Gawiser et al. 2007). Most LAE samples have so far been constructed from narrowband imaging (e.g. Hu & McMahon 1996; Rhoads et al. 2000; Ouchi et al. 2003; Shibuya et al. 2012; Sobral et al. 2017; Ouchi et al. 2018), but significant efforts need to be spent on confirming LAE candidates by spectroscopy. LAE samples have also been built from large multi-object spectroscopic surveys (Stark et al. 2010; Cassata et al. 2015), but to be efficient, such samples rely (by construction) on a very stringent photometric preselection of high-redshift candidates. The all-in-one approach of using TARSIS as a survey instrument obviates the need of any pre-selection and follow-up spectroscopy (see below). Previous results include a measurement of the clustering properties of LAEs (Diener et al. 2017), an estimate of the Ly α

emitting fraction among high-redshift galaxies (Caruana et al. 2018) and a determination of the Ly α luminosity function (Herenz et al. 2019).

As a result of these studies, the number of detected Ly α emitting objects –even at the highest observable redshifts– has increased impressively (e.g., the latest detection of ~ 2000 Ly α emitters at $z \sim 6 - 7$ Ouchi et al. 2017; also see Barnes et al. 2014 for a list of Ly α surveys), and the quality of the detections has improved significantly. This development has not only lead to the discovery of new types of astrophysical objects such as ‘Lyman- α blobs’ (e.g., Francis et al. 1996; Fynbo et al. 1999; Steidel et al. 2000; North et al. 2017), ‘giant Ly α halos’ (e.g., Cantalupo et al. 2014; Hennawi et al. 2015; Cai et al. 2016), and ‘extreme equivalent width objects’ (e.g., Sobral et al. 2015) but also opened up the chance of statistical usage of Ly α data, for example, to constrain the ‘Epoch of Reionization’ (see review by Dijkstra 2014) or the leakage of ionizing photons (e.g., Dijkstra et al. 2016; Verhamme et al. 2017). The unprecedented sensitivity of MUSE has already revealed the ubiquity of Ly α emission throughout the Universe (Bacon et al. 2015; Wisotzki et al. 2016; Drake et al. 2017), and the combination of imaging with spectral information opens many new possibilities for Ly α data analysis, which will provide further understanding of these Ly α -emitting objects.

With its blue spectral coverage and increased FoV, TARSIS will be a powerful facility to observe LAE at redshifts between $1.6 < z < 3.0$. This epoch is a key period of cosmic history, as the star formation density reached peaks and then turned around to decrease with time (see Figure 24; Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.).

Figure 24: Left: Cosmic SFR density as a function of redshift (the Cosmic Noon is seen between $1.5 < z < 3$). Right: Evolution of the star formation rate density for LAE (de La Vieuville et al. 2019).

Based on the Garel et al. (2016) and the emission line sensitivity of TARSIS (see Section 8.2), we expect over 165 detections of LAEs per completed pointing of CATARSIS, considering a TARSIS FoV of 7.4 arcmin^2 (i.e., $\sim 2.8 \times 2.8 \text{ arcmin}^2$ but also excluding the small gap between quadrants). This means that CATARSIS will double current samples of LAEs.

4.1.3 The faint-end of the LAE luminosity function

LAEs are now commonly found up to a redshift of $z \sim 7$, allowing us to study the formation and evolution of galaxies in the early universe. Most LAEs have been extensively probed in narrowband imaging surveys (e.g., Hu et al. 1998; Rhoads et al. 2000; Shimasaku et al. 2006; Ouchi et al. 2008) and blind spectroscopic searches that have led to hundreds of detections, especially in this century (Rauch et al. 2008; Cassata et al. 2011; Blanc et al. 2011). These observations have mainly put statistical constraints on the bright part of the Ly α luminosity function and its clustering, and they tend to show that LAEs are slightly less massive, bluer and more metal-poor than the other well-studied high- redshift galaxy populations, the Lyman-Break galaxies or "drop-out" galaxies (Shapley et al. 2001, 2003; Pentericci et al. 2007; Bouwens et al. 2009). However, the existing Ly α data remains somewhat more inhomogeneous than that of dropout galaxies, due to the different selection methods used in various surveys, potential significant contamination, and rather small statistics. Therefore, we do not yet have a complete picture of the characteristics of the LAE population. Furthermore, previous surveys have covered small regions of the sky and, therefore, our knowledge of the LAE population is potentially affected by the cosmological variance.

Figure 25; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** shows the LAE luminosity function at different redshifts, together with the predictions of semi-analytical models with different cloud geometries. Deep CATARSIS observations will detect Ly α fluxes of $\sim 10^{-17}$ erg s $^{-1}$ without considering possible magnifications due to the cluster lenses. This translates into $L_{\text{Ly}\alpha} \approx 1.8 \times 10^{40}$ erg s $^{-1}$ at $z = 1.6$ and 1.6×10^{42} erg s $^{-1}$ at $z = 3$.

Figure 25: LAE luminosity function at $z = 2.2$ (top left), 3.0, (top right), 5.7 (bottom left) and 6.7 (bottom right). The luminosity function computed for different geometries is plotted as colored continuum lines, in blue for the Wind geometry, in red for the Bicone geometry and in green the Thin-Shell geometry. The intrinsic Ly α luminosity function is plotted in continuum black. The black dashed lines show the combined luminosity function that is fitted. At $z=2.2$ we also show the luminosity function observed by Konno et al. (2016) (blue dots), Sobral et al. (2017) (purple diamonds) and Cassata et al. (2011) (green squares). At $z = 3$ we show the luminosity function observed by Cassata et al (2015) (green squares) and Ouchi et al.

[2008](#) (blue dots). At $z = 5.7$ and $z = 6.7$ we show the luminosity functions observed by Ouchi et al. (2008) (blue dots) and Konno et al. (2018) (purple diamonds).

4.1.4 Measuring the properties of LAE in CATARSIS

We will characterise the kinematics, chemical abundances of the galaxies, and quantify the presence of outflows using other UV lines. For objects at redshifts between $1.6 < z < 2.5$, the most prominent transitions are [C III] $\lambda 1907$, C III] $\lambda 1909$, O III] $\lambda \lambda 1661, 66$, Si III] $\lambda \lambda 1883, 92$, NV $\lambda 1240$ and Si $\lambda 1400$, C IV $\lambda \lambda 1548, 1551$, N II] $\lambda \lambda 1750, 52$, and MgII $\lambda 2796$ for galaxies at $z < 1.9$, although some of these transitions show the complex profiles of combined stellar and nebular origin; CIV $\lambda \lambda 1548, 1551$, HeII 1640, (Stark et al. 2015; Maseda et al. 2017; Senchyna et al. 2017; Vanzella et al. 2016; Mainali et al. 2017; Berg et al. 2018).

Metallicity can be calculated with the $[\text{N II}]\lambda\lambda 2139, 2143 / [\text{O II}]\lambda 2470$ and the C II and C III lines (Kewley et al. 2019). Furthermore, starburst galaxies produce strong interstellar absorption lines, stellar photospheric and wind lines, some of which are sensitive to the metallicity (Rix et al. 2004; Leitherer et al. 2011; Zetterlund et al. 2015; see also Figure 26). Ionization parameters, on the other hand can be obtained with $([\text{C III}]\lambda 1908 \text{ blend}) / ([\text{C II}]\lambda 2325 \text{ blend})$ or $([\text{O III}]\lambda 1666 + [\text{O III}]\lambda 1660) / ([\text{O II}]\lambda 2470.22 \text{ blend})$.

With the prospect of observing more than 57,000 LAEs over a 1.7 square degrees area, the sample will be large enough to properly characterize these objects, without the systematic errors due to the cosmic variance.

Figure 26: The dependence of the CIV 1550Å (left panels) and NV 1240Å (right panels) profiles on stellar age and metallicity. The observed stellar wind profile from s0033+042 is shown in gray in each panel.

4.1.5 The emission of the Circumgalactic medium

Ultraviolet absorption-line spectroscopy remains the most efficient and sensitive means of studying the diffuse gas that permeates the universe. This gas, commonly referred to as the intergalactic medium (IGM) or Ly α forest, is the dominant reservoir of baryons in the universe at all epochs (Prochaska & Tumlinson 2008). It provides fresh fuel for star formation and collects the radiation and metals produced by galaxies and AGN. Furthermore, the IGM is expected to trace the DM distribution of the LSS, offering unique constraints on our cosmological paradigm (e.g., Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996; Rauch 1998; McDonald et al. 2006; Viel et al. 2009).

By studying the IGM we can obtain information about crucial, but poorly understood processes, like gas accretion into galaxies, galactic winds driven by feedback from star formation and/or accreting SMBHs. Our sensitivity limits will allow the detection of Ly α , Si III λ 1206 and Si IV λ 1394,1403 at $z = 1.65$, probing the cold accretion flows and colder parts of outflows, and CIV λ 1548,1551 as a powerful tracer of the diffuse warm-hot IGM and galactic winds (Bertone & Schaye 2012). This will allow us to disentangle the nature of Lyman- α blobs, which are huge concentrations of gas emitting Ly α whose nature is still unknown (Steidel et al. 2000; Yang et al. 2009). This line emission might be due to cooling radiation from gas in-falling onto haloes, galactic winds driven by SNe explosions or recombination radiation due to internal sources (e.g., Fardal et al. 2001; Geach et al. 2009). The detection or not of metal line emission from the same gas phase that produces Ly α radiation would help revealing the nature of the blobs.

Figure 27: The rest-frame UV emission of the IGM (i.e., gas with $n_H < 10^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) at $z = 2$ (upper panels), 3 (upper-middle panels), 4 (lower-middle panels) and 5 (bottom panels). From left to right: emissions from HI Ly α , HI Ly α SS (i.e. HI Ly α from gas with $n_H < 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), HeII H α , CIII, and CIV. The maps show a zoom of a region of $4 h^{-1}$ (comoving) Mpc on a side that contains a group forming at the intersection of a web of filaments. All maps use a pixel size of 2 arcsec. The number of pixels shown in each panel is 1082, 872, 762 and 692 at $z = 2, 3, 4$ and 5, respectively. A given color corresponds to the same surface brightness

level in all panels. The minimum and maximum values used for the color scale do not correspond to the actual minimum and maximum. Predictions by Bertone & Schaye (2012).

4.1.6 Counterparts of Damped Lyman-alpha

Little is known about the properties of DLAs (masses or SFRs), because investigations have been primarily limited to pencil-beam line-of-sight observations through the cloud. The detection rate of emission counterparts of DLAs has been low (~10%, e.g., Fynbo et al. 2013) due, partially, to the use of long-slit spectroscopy that can miss the emission depending on the orientation. CATARSIS observations will allow to analyze the structure of the (most) extended Ly α emission, estimate SFRs for these galaxies accounting for the missing emission from long-slit observations, and search for signs of outflows/inflows in Ly α . CATARSIS will be able to observe Ly α from $z=1.6$ to 3.28 , a range that includes the peak of the DLAs redshift distribution ($z\sim 2.5-3.0$), which is not reached by any other IFU facility (VLT-MUSE allows observations of DLA at $z > 2.9$). Furthermore, in low metallicity DLAs, we will be able to measure the abundance of CNO, which has only been possible for a handful of objects (Pettini et al. 2008). The N/O and C/O ratios may reveal important clues about the IMF universality and the origin of metals in the IGM.

4.2 Dissecting HeII emitters: spectral templates for sources of the Cosmic Dawn

Cosmic dawn ($7 < z < 10$) marks a major phase transition of the Universe, during which the first stars (so-called Population III) and the subsequent formation of low-mass, extremely metal-poor galaxies put an end to the dark ages. The details of the reionisation history reflect the nature of these first sources, which is currently completely unconstrained and the subject of considerable observational and theoretical efforts. Rest-frame UV long-slit spectra of $z\sim 5-7$ galaxies have revealed prominent high-ionization nebular emission lines (i.e., OIII], CIII], CIV, HeII) indicating that extreme radiation fields characterize reionization-era galaxies (e.g., Stark 2016; Mainali et al. 2018). Theoretical arguments suggest that PopIII stars (Woolf 1965) and nearly metal-free ($Z < Z_{\odot}/100$) stars have spectra hard enough to produce many He⁺-ionizing photons. Thus, the high-ionization HeII line is suggested to be an excellent diagnostic to identify the elusive galaxies hosting PopIII stars (e.g., Visbal et al. 2015).

Indeed, metal-poor star-forming galaxies show, in general, stronger and narrower nebular HeII $\lambda\lambda 1640, 4686$ emissions compared to those of higher metallicities (e.g., Guseva et al. 2000; Senchyna et al. 2017). However, the emission seems to be too strong to be produced by the number of forming stars present in the galaxy. Alternatives like rotation of massive stars, binarity or variations in the IMF have been proposed, but despite much observational and theoretical effort, HeII ionization keeps being a longstanding mystery specially in metal-deficient galaxies (Garnett et al. 1991; Kehrig et al. 2011, 2015, 2018; Cassata et al. 2013; Senchyna et al. 2017) and keeps challenging current models for hot massive stars which include relevant advances as binarity and rotation effects (e.g., Leitherer et al. 2014; Gotberg et al. 2018; Eldridge et al. 2017; Stanway & Eldridge 2019).

JWST has just started studying the integrated properties of sources identified at this epoch. However, observing the UV photons gets progressively more difficult at $z \gtrsim 7$ due to the increasing opacity of the IGM (e.g., Dijkstra et al. 2011). Even JWST will only be able to study in detail (spectroscopically) the brightest sources $z \gtrsim 7$ (that are potentially responsible for

reionisation, e.g., Bouwens et al. [2015](#)) will remain prohibitive. Another alternative is to identify reionization-era analogues at lower redshifts that are bright enough for high-quality spatially resolved spectroscopy.

To advance this topic we need to increase the number of spectroscopic observations of HeII-emitting systems and CATARSIS will play an important role in this game. Due to the wide FoV and spectral range (3200–8100Å) of TARSIS we will serendipitously identify new HeII emitters in the CATARSIS fields. This will allow us to perform detailed galaxy-by-galaxy study of the HeII-emitting gas and ionizing sources necessary and sufficient to power high-ionizing emissions. For $z \sim 0$ HeII-emitters, we will have access to the relevant lines ([OII] $\lambda\lambda 3726, 3729\text{\AA}$, H γ , [OIII] $\lambda 4363\text{\AA}$, HeII $\lambda 4686\text{\AA}$, H β , [OIII] $\lambda 5007\text{\AA}$) to derive physical-chemical properties (e.g., extinction, temperature, metallicity). For more distant ($z \sim 1.0-1.7$) HeII-emitting galaxies, we will be able to study the properties of the ISM using relevant emission lines (HeII $\lambda 1640$, CIV] $\lambda 1550$, OIII] $\lambda 1665$, CIII] $\lambda 1909$) through, for instance, UV line-ratio diagnostics (e.g., Feltre et al. [2016](#)). Similar methods to those used by Kehrig et al. ([2015](#), [2018](#)) will be employed to analyze CATARSIS data. Broad HeII emission, usually attributed to WR stellar winds, can have FWHM as low as $\sim 800 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ in low-metallicity environments (e.g., Crowther & Hadfield [2006](#)). Disentangling the broad from the narrow components of the HeII emission line is essential to carry out this project. The spectral resolution of TARSIS is sufficient to resolve these HeII lines.

4.3 Lensed galaxies

The high magnification by clusters allows their use as “cosmic telescopes” to study background galaxies. Some of the highest redshift galaxies known were discovered as magnified sources in the fields of massive strong-lensing clusters (e.g., Zheng et al. [2012](#); Coe et al. [2013](#); Zitrin et al. [2014](#); Watson et al. [2015](#); Salmon et al. [2018](#)). At intermediate redshifts, some of the best-studied star-forming galaxies are those that are magnified by gravitational lensing, which enables high signal-to-noise measurements (e.g., Pettini et al. [2000](#), [2002](#); Dessauges-Zavadsky et al. [2011](#); Rigby et al. [2018](#)), and probes sub-galactic scales (Whitaker et al. [2014](#)). Magnifications caused by the gravity of strong lensing clusters can exceed factors of hundreds if galaxies are fortuitously placed near a lensing caustic. Measuring a large number of redshifts of multiple images in a cluster has only been possible routinely with the MUSE instrument, thus revolutionizing the cluster lensing modelling power (e.g., Lagattuta et al. [2017](#)), with potential further application to put constraints on the properties of DM cross-section (e.g., Harvey et al. [2017](#)) or cosmological parameters (e.g., Jullo et al. [2010](#)). Using these precise models, we can then correct for the lensing magnification of distant sources, thus extracting their full properties.

By probing the redshift range $1.63 < z < 3$ in Ly α , we expect a much larger number of background sources than MUSE has found in the Frontier Field Survey due to its much redder wavelength coverage (a factor ~ 5 based on the LAE luminosity function by Garel et al. [2016](#)). Half of the clusters in our CATARSIS sample are acting as strong lenses for galaxies in the background.

5. SYNERGIES WITH OTHER FACILITIES

CATARSIS clusters will be observed at 1.1, 1.4 and 2 mm with the TolTEC camera (Wilson et al. [2020](#)) on the 50m Large Millimeter Telescope (Hughes et al. [2020](#)) to trace the density distribution of the ICM through the detection of the Sunyaev-Zel’dovich (SZ) effect, the distortion

on the CMB photon energy distribution induced by inverse-Compton scattering off the ICM hot free electrons.

The relatively high angular resolution of the TolTEC SZE observations (~ 6 arcsec at 1.1mm) will potentially detect pressure discontinuities in the ICM (i.e., shocks) produced by the merging of substructures, and probe the gas dynamics and astrophysical processes out to the low-density regions in the outskirts of galaxy clusters (Mroczkowski et al. 2019). These mm-wavelength observations will therefore complement those from CATARSIS to provide a multi-wavelength picture of the mass assembly of clusters and the growth of structure. Furthermore, mm-wavelength observations are sensitive to the dust and the obscured star-formation in galaxies. Optical-UV observations are known to underestimate the total SFR of dusty galaxies, even when mid-IR data (e.g., 24 μm MIPS/Spitzer) are available. The combination of CATARSIS and TolTEC/LMT follow-up observations will therefore allow us to understand the process of star formation and its impact on the evolution of galaxies within large scale structures more accurately.

Observations with the suite of heterodyne instruments of the LMT towards samples of galaxies identified by CATARSIS will trace their cold molecular gas to better understand the mass build-up in galaxies over time (e.g., Cybulski et al. 2016). Since clusters of galaxies act as strong gravitational lenses, targeted observations towards these massive structures increase the probability of serendipitously discovering faint distant galaxies, which are elusive to current mm-wavelength facilities (e.g., Pope et al. 2017). This population of galaxies, with modest SFR ($\sim 10 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), is expected to dominate the SFH of the Universe at $z > 2$. Having access to Optical-UV and mm-wavelengths data is therefore crucial to have a complete view of the SFH and better understand the impact of dust at high redshifts.

6. SCIENCE CASES OUTSIDE CATARSIS

Although the call from the CAHA Observatory was to carry out a survey and TARSIS was selected specifically for carrying out the CATARSIS survey, we have collected some science cases outside CATARSIS to illustrate the versatility of TARSIS and its usefulness for a variety of different science cases, not only in the field of “galaxies and cosmology” but also for studies of stellar evolution and classification, the ISM, or the Solar System.

6.1 Stellar evolution Science Cases

6.1.1 Spectral classification of stars in OB-Type clusters (J. Maíz Apellániz - CAB)

Gaia is allowing us to identify the membership in stellar clusters but the wavelength region it uses for its spectrograph is the Ca triplet window, where few useful lines exist for OB stars. The blue spectrographs in TARSIS could be used to spectroscopically characterize those stars, as the blue-violet region is rich in OB stellar lines. As this case does not require spectrophotometric calibrations, it can be done under poor conditions and even be used as a filler program. Each cluster could be covered in a time scale of 1 hour for compact systems to several hours for more extended ones. As there are several tens of OB clusters to be analyzed, the case could be applied to a fraction of the sample or to the full one as a filler program. In this case the advantage of TARSIS is the access to the whole blue-violet spectral region using a large IFS on a 3.5 m telescope.

6.1.2 A new view of the evolution of metal-poor massive stars with TARSIS (M. García - CAB)

The role of massive stars as dynamizing agents of the Universe begins already at the reionization epoch, being among the first sources capable of providing a strong field of UV photons. Since there on, characterizing the evolution of galaxies and the Cosmos relies on our knowledge of the physics of massive stars, which must be provided as a function of the varying environment and extended to the conditions of the early Universe.

One of the most important parameters changing in the evolution of the Universe is metallicity, ever increasing since the formation of the first stars. Our current standard for low metallicity is the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC), with about 1/5 of the solar value. That is far from the very low metallicities of the early Universe and even from the metallicity of the peak of star formation, that does not exceed $Z_{\odot}/10$ (Madau & Dickinson 2014). Efforts are being made to surpass the SMC frontier by characterizing massive stars in Local Group and nearby galaxies with metal content akin to earlier stages of the Universe (García et al. 2019), but progress is slow due to their distance (≥ 750 kpc). Photometric candidates must first be confirmed with low-resolution spectroscopy, which requires long observing programs on multi-object spectrographs and has the risk of interesting stars slipping through the photometric cuts.

The interest in metal-poor massive stars has been revitalized by the results from the revolutionary LIGO and VIRGO experiments. The masses of the black holes (BH) whose collapse has been registered by gravitational wave (GW) events evince the possibility that massive stars keep most of their mass until the end of their evolution, leading to pre-BH masses 20 or 30 M_{\odot} larger than previously predicted by stellar evolution models (Abbott et al. 2016). Since massive stars lose mass to radiation-driven winds (RDWs), propelled by absorption and re-scatter of photons by metallic ions, this new scenario immediately invokes metal-poor chemical composition with the ensuing weaker winds.

Re-visiting the evolution of massive stars within binary systems has also led to interesting new channels. In particular, there is a new view according to which long-known post-main sequence stages such as Be stars, Red Supergiants (RSG), Luminous Blue Variables (LBV), and Wolf-Rayet stars (WR), could be the result of the interaction of two stars within a binary system (Beasar et al. 2020; Göteborg et al. 2018). This emerging scenario is in line with the detection of isolated WR/LBV stars in metal-poor galaxies (Herrero et al. 2010; Trammer et al. 2015), hard to explain in the context of RDWs. However, there is much work ahead to characterize the mass donors and gainers within the system, and the relative incidence of these stellar classes due to binary *versus* classical-single star evolution (Shenar et al. 2020). The interest of these findings exceeds the academic interest on massive star evolution and impact the estimated production of ionizing photons and kinetic energy by a stellar population, the estimated rates of SNe/GRBs within a galaxy, the inferred IMF from integrated populations, and the interpretation of nebular lines in distant galaxies.

Yet, the incidence of binary stars, and their typical period and mass fractions, is uncharted territory beyond the Magellanic Clouds. The Local Group and nearby galaxies could enable us to explore this topic but only a couple of binary stars have been confirmed in these systems. Again,

the main reason is that the distance to the galaxies impose strict sensitivity requirements that make multi-epoch observations prohibitive.

A large field of view IFU such as TARSIS can help us advance significantly in our studies of metal-poor massive stars. On the one hand it will enable untargeted studies of galaxies, enlarging the scarcely populated catalogs of metal-poor massive stars while fully sampling the upper IMF. On the other hand, it will enable multi-epoch observations and the detection of spectroscopic binaries in Local Group galaxies.

We therefore envision observations of massive stars in star-forming regions in Local Group galaxies accessible from Calar Alto (and with a density adequate to the TARSIS spaxel size), covering a range in metallicity from the Large Magellanic Cloud (as anchor point) to well beyond the Small Magellanic Cloud. Our previous work on these galaxies will allow us to identify the best suited regions to obtain significant statistical information on metal-poor massive stars and on their massive binary population.

6.1.3 Structure of Extended Planetary Nebulae (M. A. Guerrero - IAA-CSIC)

Planetary nebulae (PNe) represent the final stages of the stellar evolution of low- and intermediate-mass stars with initial mass from 1 to 8 M_{\odot} (Kwok 2000). These short-lived nebulae encode information on the chemical enrichment of the progenitor stars and their yields to the interstellar medium to contribute to the chemical evolution of galaxies. Their characteristic emission line spectra make them easily detectable in external galaxies (or even in the ICM of clusters of galaxies) where they can be used to trace the kinematics and chemical abundances and to be used as secondary distance indicators (Ciardullo et al. 1989).

The spectral coverage and resolution of TARSIS are ideally suited for spectral analysis of PNe to investigate their physical conditions and key abundances ratios such as He/H, O/H, N/O and Ne/O among others. Compared to “traditional” long-slit and small-sized integral field spectroscopy, the large field of view of TARSIS will be a game changer in the investigation of the largest structures of PNe, low surface brightness haloes surrounding the bright main PNe (Chu et al. 1987). These haloes correspond to material ejected during the final stages of the asymptotic giant branch, most likely associated with thermal pulses (Stanghellini & Pasqualli 1995), so they can be used to diagnose the chemical evolution on the surface of low- and intermediate-mass stars as the result of the second and third dredge-up (Monreal-Ibero et al. 2005).

The large FoV of TARSIS can also be used to investigate PNe in resolved external galaxies. These investigations are traditionally performed on a two-step way, the first one in imaging mode to detect the population of PNe (e.g., Merrett et al. 2006) and the second one in a follow-up spectroscopic mode to characterize them (Kwitter et al. 2012; Fang et al. 2015). TARSIS observations can go through the whole process in a single step, identifying the population of PNe and obtaining spectral information of them simultaneously. The results derived from the population of PNe can be added to those obtained from other galactic components (stars, dust, ionized nebulae) in the same observation.

6.1.4 Extinction law in OB clusters (J. Maíz Apellániz - CAB)

Most of the previous work on the topic has been done with photometry, not with spectrophotometry, so the detailed behavior with wavelength is poorly constrained. TARSIS allows for the simultaneous observation of some cluster stars using the blue spectrographs and others using the red spectrograph. Using either a rotating ("Staring mode") or mapping ("Mapping mode") strategy, it should be possible to cover an OB cluster (including calibrations) with ~10 useful stars in ~1 hour. Therefore, using 1-2 nights we could produce a significant sample of 100-200 stars with 3200-8100Å spectrophotometry and derive the extinction law (and its variations) in that region. This case would require photometric conditions to be carried out. The biggest advantage of TARSIS with respect to other spectrographs for this case is the easy access to the U band.

6.2 Solar System Science

6.2.1 Structure and properties of Small Bodies in the Solar System (R. Duffard et al - IAA)

CATARSIS is a survey optimized for extra-galactic astronomy and cosmology, aimed at obtaining deep spectroscopy of galaxy clusters and filaments at $z \sim 0.15-0.23$ through selected pointings. Its proposed observational strategy favors higher-quality data in the bluer range (320-520nm) rather than in the redder part (510-810nm). Serendipitous observations of small bodies (SB) of the Solar System can be considered as transient phenomena due to their apparent motion in the sky that will produce random observations in some pointings. The most interesting data that TARSIS will provide us in the context of the Solar-System science is in the blue range, as this has not been thoroughly explored yet because most of the attention has been directed to the red and near-infrared spectra where absorption features of silicates and ices appear.

Random observations of Small Bodies within CATARSIS may lead to the observation of extended objects, perhaps surrounded by a coma due to cometary-like activity. Some cometary emission lines of interest appear in the 320-520nm region, in particular lines of C2, NH₂, and CN (e.g., Brown et al. [1996](#)), although most will be blended due to the moderate resolving power of TARSIS. On the other hand, the IFU capabilities can be used to study the morphological properties of these extended objects in regions close to the nucleus. The redder part of the spectrum will also be interesting to characterize the continuum of the spectra.

6.3 Targets of Opportunity

6.3.1 CAHA response to GW alerts (A. Carramiñana - INAOE)

August 17th, 2017 represented an unforgivable event in the history of astrophysics, thanks to the detection, for the first time, of the electromagnetic (EM) counterpart of a Gravitational Wave detection event, GW170817 (Abbott et al. [2017](#); Pian et al. [2017](#); Smartt et al. [2017](#)), that was caused by the merger of two neutron stars (NS-NS event). As a highlight of its relevance is worth noting that during the period between August and September 2017 a total of 5,000 images and spectra were taken with the 14 instruments of the seven ESO telescopes (Levan & Jonker [2020](#)).

That moment represented the crack of the starter's pistol for the race for being first and being best in detecting these EM counterparts, even although it had already started back in 2015 with the detection of the first BH-BH GW event with LIGO+VIRGO (GW150914; Abbott et al. [2016](#)).

The onset of GW170817 set a level for the LIGO+VIRGO NS-NS detection rate of 1.5 yr^{-1} within 100 Mpc^3 (with 90% credible range of $0.3\text{-}4.7 \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Abbott et al. 2017). The Advanced LIGO/Virgo detector was sensitive to NS-NS mergers up to 70-100 Mpc. Indeed, the GW170817 (NGC 4993) is an early-type galaxy with sub-solar metallicity at an approximate distance of 40-45 Mpc, depending on the distance estimator used (see Hjorth et al. 2017). The actual GW170817 NS-NS counterpart was found $\sim 2 \text{ kpc}$ ($0.64 \times R_{\text{eff}}$) away from the galaxy center (see Figure 28).

Since the most efficient EM-counterpart identification strategy as of today is to target the most-probable hosts (based on the position and redshift probability distributions of the GW event and the host's stellar mass content and SFH; see Belczynski et al. 2018), having the possibility of directly catching the EM-counterpart in spectroscopy with a wide-FoV IFU such as TARSIS would allow to be first and to be best in this race. In that regard, TARSIS would put the CAHA 3.5m as a unique facility for following up this kind of NS-NS events without the need of carrying out pre-imaging or even of comparing these imaging observations with previous imaging data. Note, that with the increase in sensitivity of future GW detectors previous imaging data might not reach the required depth to perform such identification, especially at high declinations where the Rubin Observatory will not be observing. Figure 28 below shows the image of NGC 4993 with the TARSIS FoV over-imposed to emphasize the unique capabilities of TARSIS for performing direct spectroscopic observations of GW EM counterparts even if they are found in hosts located significantly closer to us than NGC 4993.

Figure 28: TARSIS FoV over-imposed on the discovery image of the EM counterpart of the GW170817 NS-NS Gravitational Wave (GW) event in nearby elliptical galaxy NGC 4993.

7. SUMMARY OF THE SCIENTIFIC REQUIREMENTS

Table 1 lists the design requirements of TARSIS in terms of FoV, spectral range per spectrograph, spaxel size, resolving power, and efficiency. The scientific requirements for each of the major science cases of CATARSIS described elsewhere in this document are listed in *Table 2*.

	Blue	Red
Field of View (FoV)	$3 \times (1.36 \times 1.36) \text{ arcmin}^2$	$1.36 \times 1.36 \text{ arcmin}^2$
Spectral range	320 nm – 520 nm	510 nm – 810 nm
Spatial resolution element	$2.05 \times 2.05 \text{ arcsec}^2$	$2.05 \times 2.05 \text{ arcsec}^2$
Resolving Power (R)	740 at 320 nm, 1030 at 420 nm, 1290 at 520 nm	750 at 510 nm, 980 at 660 nm, 1210 at 810 nm
Total average efficiency without the telescope (but including slicer + spectrograph + detector)	$\geq 20\%$	$\geq 30\%$

Table 1: Main characteristics of the two sets of spectrographs of the TARSIS instrument.

SCIENCE CASE	WAVELENGTH COVERAGE (320-810nm)	FOV (9 arcmin ²)	SPECTRAL RESOLUTION (R~1000)
Clusters Mass Profiles	NOT CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL
Substructure, infall groups	NOT CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL
Mass accretion history	NOT CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL
Intracluster light	NOT CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL
Galaxy alignments	NOT CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL
Velocity dispersion function	NOT CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL
Detailed SFH	CRITICAL	DESIRABLE	CRITICAL
Chemical evolution of clusters and galaxies	CRITICAL	DESIRABLE	CRITICAL
Evolution of the IMF	CRITICAL	DESIRABLE	CRITICAL
Chemical abundances in stars and gas	CRITICAL	DESIRABLE	CRITICAL
SN Ia yields	CRITICAL	DESIRABLE	CRITICAL
Serendipitous science	CRITICAL	CRITICAL	CRITICAL

Table 2: Summary of the broad scientific requirements imposed by the CATARSIS survey and level of criticality of each for the science cases described above.

7.1 Justification of the most critical scientific requirements

The two requirements that have been a major challenge when designing the instrument and that have a significant impact on the final budget are (1) the short blue limit of the wavelength range ($\lambda = 3200\text{\AA}$) and its optimization of the instrument in the blue, and (2) its large FoV (2.8 arcmin

$\times 2.8$ arcmin). At the same time, those are the features that make this instrument unique and the ones that make CATARSIS scientifically strong. Besides, we also require (see Table 1 above) to reach a moderate spectral resolution or $R \sim 1000$ for most of the TARSIS wavelength range and the highest efficiency compatible with these previous top-level requirements.

7.1.1 Blue coverage and FoV

One of the characteristics that makes TARSIS unique is the wavelength coverage. Its wavelength range allows to study the rest/frame NUV in the spectra of our targeted galaxy clusters. We have shown that thanks to this wavelength range we can detect very small amounts ($< 1\%$) of star formation and study the timescales of star formation quenching with a precision that will allow, for the first time, to distinguish between the different physical processes responsible for it. The optical region does not have sensibility to detect small amounts of star formation and the SFR indicators, like the $H\alpha$ luminosity, become undetectable for SFRs below a certain threshold.

The extension to the blue part of the spectra will allow us to study differences in the chemistry of young and old stars, compare chemical abundances in the stellar and ionized gas components and explore the variations of the IMF with metallicity and SFR (see Section 3.2). These projects will not be feasible without having access to rest-frame wavelengths $< 3000\text{\AA}$.

It is also thanks to the wavelength coverage that we will be able to observe the $Ly\alpha$ transition at redshifts $z \simeq 1.6$, and characterize their properties measuring chemical abundances, ionization parameters and kinematics. Without the NUV we would not be able to observe, simultaneously, the $Ly\alpha$ and $MgII \lambda\lambda 2780$ transitions, that gives us the possibility to study the escape fraction using other resonant lines. Being able to observe $Ly\alpha$ at such low redshifts gives us a clear advantage over other surveys, as it is since $z \lesssim 1.9$ that the cosmic SFR density starts to decrease. This wavelength range, together with the large FoV is what makes this project competitive even when compared with other projects carried out at 8-m class telescopes.

7.1.2 Integral Field Spectrograph with a large field of view

Almost all the science cases described in Section 2 rely on obtaining a sufficiently dense coverage of redshifts covering the whole extension of the clusters. The large number of redshifts for an unbiased sample of galaxies will allow to characterize substructure, identify interlopers or measure anisotropy, which in turn will allow us to reduce to the minimum existing biases in the determination of cluster mass profiles. Mapping the outskirts of clusters will also give us access to the calculation of accretion rates and the splashback radius, as well as to study the alignments of galaxies with respect to the filaments. These regions represent more than 90% of the cluster volume and the corresponding projected area in the sky and mapping them with a smaller FoV will extend the duration of the survey to unfeasible timescales.

For substructure determination and for the study of galaxy transformations is especially important to observe unbiased samples of galaxies, without having to pre-select galaxies with certain properties, motivating the building of an IFS instead of a multi-object spectrograph covering a larger FoV.

Furthermore, astronomy is to a large degree still driven by unexpected discoveries and the probability of serendipitous discovery is proportional to the field of view. It is for this that TARSIS, with its 2.8 arcmin x 2.8 arcmin field of view, has an enormous potential to discover.

As we mentioned above, the efficiency of the survey is largely determined by the large FoV, and this requirement put some limits to spatial resolution of the instrument, 2.05×2.05 arcsec². However, a higher resolving power would not be optimal for medium observing conditions, as a significant fraction of a point-source light would not fit a single spaxel when convolved with the Point Spread Function (PSF), lowering the detection limit of faint emission lines (see Table 3). Although the signal can be increasing by adding spaxels, this would result in a penalty in the final signal-to-noise ratio. This is also the case for extended sources with low surface brightness (i.e., ICL emission and outer parts of galaxies, see Sections 3.1.2 & 3.1.2), where the desired signal-to-noise ratio can only be reached after binning the datacubes.

Seeing (") (r-band)	Seeing (") (320nm)	%PSF inside 1x1" SPX	%PSF inside 2"x 2" SPX
0.6	0.8	73%	99%
0.8	1.0	57%	96%
1.1	1.5	31%	77%
1.5	2.0	19%	57%

Table 3: Percentage of light in a PSF for different seeing fitting inside spaxels of 1x1" and 2x2".

8. JUSTIFICATION OF THE REQUESTED OBSERVING TIME

Below we describe the observing plan for each cluster and the justification for the exposure time. The total observing time and distribution throughout the 6 years of the survey is described as part of the Operational Concept Document (R.1).

8.1 Description of the sample and the observing plan

The CATARSIS survey does not aim to observe a complete sample of clusters with a particular selection function, because its scientific goals are not statistical per se. There are many ongoing and forthcoming surveys that are collecting a very large sample of clusters for that purpose. CATARSIS results, though, will be of vital importance to understand the biases and systematics associated with the different methodologies that will be used in those surveys to infer cosmological parameters. These biases and systematics effects are related with both, local and global properties of the different components, recent history, and projection effects, among others.

We have selected a total of 33 high-priority clusters (CTRS01 through CTRS33) that cover a range of these characteristics and that are, therefore, representative of the physical conditions that we expect to find in massive clusters. The clusters are selected in a redshift range from $z = 0.15$ to $z = 0.25$ because it optimizes the number of pointings to cover a large area of the clusters, rest-frame bluest wavelength edge (280-320 nm) for studies of stellar populations and chemical evolution and the signal-to-noise ratio achievable with TARSIS on the 3.5m telescope at CAHA.

To better illustrate the feasibility of the observing plan and describe the strategies described in R.1 (and also in R.2), we have defined a subsample of 16 galaxies that constitute the *Golden Sample* and for which we are also intensively pursuing complementary observations at other wavelengths. However, the final sample can slightly change as new ancillary data supporting our science goals become available or if we encounter problems during early phases of operation that requires include different targets with specific characteristics.

The sample selected is distributed in the sky so to ensure a good coverage from CAHA throughout the entire year with airmasses that do not go above airmass=1.22 (zenith distance < 35°), where the $A_{320\text{nm}}$ atmospheric extinction would be less than ~0.2 mag higher than that at the zenith (~0.9-1 mag). Document R.3 describes our study of the UV attenuation at the CAHA site developed as part of this feasibility study (WP9).

The planification of the individual pointings for the *Golden Sample* are provided as links in the TARSIS webpage (<https://guaix.ucm.es/tarsis>). These figures include information on the cluster ID, redshift and R_{200} (arcmin) at the top left corner of the plot (see also Table 4 below), the positions of all square-shaped pointings proposed for observation as part of CATARSIS, together with the positions of cluster galaxies with available spectra and those targets with SDSS magnitude $r < 22$ mag that we expect to observe with CATARSIS. The position of QSO+AGN in the *Million Quasars Catalog* (MILLIQUAS; Flesch 2015).

ID (1)	RA (deg) (J2000) (3)	DEC (deg) (J2000) (4)	$2 \times R_{200}$ (°) (5)	z (6)
CTRS01	006.136	+33.207	0.114	0.226
CTRS02	010.961	+20.667	0.1421	0.195
CTRS03	014.001	+26.342	0.2279	0.197
CTRS06	120.237	+36.056	0.1365	0.288
CTRS08	126.938	+34.790	0.1905	0.160
CTRS09	135.175	+20.895	0.0955	0.229
CTRS14	154.265	+39.047	0.2187	0.206
CTRS18	179.342	+33.632	0.1694	0.215
CTRS19	194.813	+27.965	0.1448	0.158
CTRS24	217.827	+35.110	0.1435	0.236
CTRS25	225.085	+21.362	0.2409	0.152
CTRS27	250.082	+46.711	0.1163	0.228
CTRS29	260.037	+27.670	0.2079	0.161
CTRS31	260.618	+32.154	0.0700	0.229
CTRS32	328.400	+17.695	0.2106	0.230
CTRS33	336.175	+18.671	0.1563	0.155
16 clusters	Mean values:		0.1734	0.201

Table 4: Mother sample of CATARSIS sample. R_{200} indicate the radius where the density of the cluster is 200 times the critical density of the Universe. More information, such as the number of paintings to cover each cluster to the first apocenter of galaxy orbits along with the coverage maps, is provided at <https://guaix.ucm.es/tarsis>.

In some of the clusters we also include in the online plots TARSIS pointing's located at the positions of filaments identified by filament-finder algorithms. These observations will be very useful to study the impact of pressure shocks encounter by the galaxies when follow into the cluster and the so-called pre-processing, when they are still no bona-fide cluster members. These observations will also be used to study the alignments between filaments and galaxies.

8.2 Justification of the requested observing time

The scientific objectives of CATARSIS require reaching continuum magnitudes $m_{AB,r} \sim 22$ mag (depending on the cluster galaxy color and redshift) and limiting line fluxes of $1-2 \times 10^{-17}$ erg s^{-1} cm^{-2} . Figure 29 shows the distribution of the mean surface brightness in the r -band for a sample of galaxies at redshifts $0.15 < z < 0.25$ from SDSS with magnitudes $21.9 < m_{AB,r} < 22.1$.

Figure 29: Distribution of surface brightness for a sample of galaxies at redshifts $0.15 < z < 0.25$ with magnitudes $21.9 < m_{AB,r} < 22.1$ mag.

We have used the ETC-42 generic exposure time calculator developed at CeSAM (*Centre de donnees Astrophysiques de Marseille*) by Gross et al. (2015) together with the total expected throughout of TARSIS and an atmospheric transmission curve of the CAHA observatory provided by Santos Pedraz (priv. comm., from Hayes & Latham 1975). This curve only covers wavelengths above 350nm so we used the transmission curve of La Palma Observatory (King 1985) to cover the range 320-350nm. The atmospheric extinction provided by the King's curve nicely coincide with the values we are obtaining in our program to characterise the UV sky at CAHA (see R.3). These values go from ~ 0.9 mag/airmass at 320nm down to 0.32 mag/airmass at 394nm. We use the sky emission spectrum obtained at the Paranal Observatory using UVES (Hanuschik 2003) since the one provided by Sánchez et al. (2007) only reached 370nm. Note that we are also running a program at the CAHA 1.23m telescope to monitor the effects of light pollution from LED urban lights at the UV end of the TARSIS wavelength coverage.

Figure 30 shows the expected S/N for an extended target at $z = 0.2$ with a Sa spiral-galaxy template. We show the values at the central wavelength of the blue and the red spectrographs, as a function of the surface brightness of the target in the r -band.

Table 5 and

Table 6 show the expected signal-to-noise ratios of emission lines for different fluxes and at different redshifts.

With these numbers, we inferred that the exposure time required on-target was 28,800 seconds (or 8 hours) for the Blue range and 9,600 seconds (2h 40min) for the Red range. Should we use "Staring mode" observations (see R.1 and R.2), we would aim to obtain the whole 8 hours per field in 5 full rotations where each rotation implies 3 individual exposures per subfield of 1,920 seconds of exposure time each. This leads to $1,920 \times 3 \times 5 = 28,800$ s in the Blue range and $1,920 \times 5 = 9,600$ s in the Red range.

Figure 30 shows the expected signal-to-noise ratio for extended targets at the central wavelength of the blue and the red spectrographs for the total exposure time, as a function of the surface brightness of the target in the r -band.

Figure 30: Left: Signal-to-noise ratio per spaxel at the central wavelength of the blue and red spectrographs (left) for an extended source at $z = 0.2$ with a Sa spiral-galaxy template (right) as a function of the r -band surface brightness.

TARSIS Blue arm – Emission-line sources															
f_λ (cgs)	λ (nm)					$Z_{Ly\alpha}$					$Z_{[OIII]3727AA}$				
	320	350	400	450	500	1.6	1.9	2.3	2.7	3.1	<0	<0	0.07	0.21	0.34
	S/N	S/N	S/N	S/N	S/N	$L_{Ly\alpha}$ (erg/s)					$L_{[OIII]3727AA}$ (erg/s)				
4E-16	14.8	37.3	65.6	70.8	90.6	6.8E42	1.0E43	1.7E43	2.4E43	3.4E43	-	-	4.8E39	5.2E40	1.6E41
2E-16	7.8	19.4	35.5	38.2	50.5	3.4E42	5.2E42	8.4E42	1.2E43	1.7E43	-	-	2.4E39	2.6E40	7.8E40
1E-16	4.0	10.0	18.6	19.9	26.9	1.7E42	2.6E42	4.2E42	6.2E42	8.7E42	-	-	1.2E39	1.3E40	3.9E40
8E-17	3.2	8.0	15.0	16.1	21.8	1.4E42	2.1E42	3.4E42	5.0E42	7.0E42	-	-	9.6E38	1.0E40	3.1E40
6E-17	2.4	6.0	11.4	12.2	16.6	1.0E42	1.6E42	2.5E42	3.7E42	5.2E42	-	-	7.2E38	7.8E39	2.3E40
4E-17	1.6	4.0	7.7	8.2	11.2	7.0E41	1.0E42	1.7E42	2.5E42	3.5E42	-	-	4.8E38	5.0E39	1.6E40
2E-17	0.8	2.0	3.9	4.1	5.7	3.5E41	5.0E41	8.0E41	1.2E42	1.7E42	-	-	2.4E38	2.5E39	8.0E39
1E-17	0.4	1.0	2.0	2.1	2.9	1.7E41	2.6E41	4.2E41	6.2E41	8.7E41	-	-	1.2E38	1.3E39	3.9E39

Table 5: Signal-to-noise ratio estimates at the peak of the line in the Blue range ($t_{exp}=28,800$ s). The combination of galaxy template and magnitude where the signal-to-noise ratio is close to 3 is marked in boldface.

TARSIS Red arm – Emission-line sources															
f_λ (cgs)	λ (nm)					$Z_{[OIII]5007A}$					$Z_{H\alpha}$				
	550	600	700	750	800	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.6	<0	<0	0.07	0.14	0.22
	S/N	S/N	S/N	S/N	S/N	$L_{[OIII]5007A}$ (erg/s)					$L_{H\alpha}$ (erg/s)				
4E-16	56.0	60.0	80.8	88.6	84.0	1.0E40	4.7E40	2.3E41	3.9E41	6.1E41	-	-	4.3E39	2.2E40	5.7E40
2E-16	31.0	32.9	46.8	52.9	49.0	5.1E39	2.3E40	1.2E41	2.0E41	3.1E41	-	-	2.2E39	1.1E40	2.9E40
1E-16	16.6	17.4	25.8	29.8	27.1	2.6E39	1.2E40	5.8E40	9.8E40	1.5E41	-	-	1.1E39	5.5E39	1.4E40
8E-17	13.4	14.1	21.0	24.5	22.2	2.1E39	9.3E39	4.6E40	7.8E40	1.2E41	-	-	8.7E38	4.4E40	1.1E40
6E-17	10.2	10.7	16.1	18.9	17.0	1.5E42	7.0E39	3.5E40	5.9E40	9.2E40	-	-	6.5E38	3.3E39	8.6E39
4E-17	6.9	7.2	11.0	13.0	11.6	1.0E39	4.7E39	2.3E40	3.9E40	6.1E40	-	-	4.3E38	2.2E39	5.7E39
2E-17	3.5	3.7	5.6	5.6	6.0	5.1E38	2.3E39	1.2E40	2.0E40	3.1E40	-	-	2.2E38	1.1E39	2.9E39
1E-17	1.8	1.8	2.9	3.4	3.0	2.6E38	1.2E39	5.8E39	9.8E39	1.5E40	-	-	1.1E38	5.5E38	1.4E39

Table 6: Signal-to-noise ratio estimates at the peak of the line in the Red range ($t_{exp}=9,600$ s). The combination of galaxy template and magnitude where the signal-to-noise ratio is close to 3 is marked in boldface.

The average R_{200} projected in the sky for massive clusters at $z = 0.15$ and $z = 0.23$ is 6.3 and 4.5 arcmin, respectively. Therefore, in order to reach $2 \times R_{200}$ with a FoV of $\sim 7,6$ arcmin² (gap excluded) we need a total of 784 pointings. Allowing for pointings in the filaments (see <https://guaix.ucm.es/tarsis> for the examples we have designed for the *Golden Sample*), we request a total of 797 pointings (see also R.2 and R.3).

In any case, we are continuing the on-site UV characterization. If the values of atmospheric extinction at 320nm turn out to be very different from what we have assumed in certain months (e.g., due to strong seasonal variations of the O_3 or salt grains in the atmosphere, or the presence of Saharan desert), we would fine-tune the sample accordingly.

8.2.1 Justification of dark night request

The analysis below justifies why CATARSIS should be executed under dark conditions, although the characteristics of the instrument are still unsurpassed in many aspects for carrying frontier (especially Galactic) science even under full moon illumination. We refer the reader to Section 6 for examples of highly competitive observing programs that could be executed during open-time bright conditions.

We have used ETC-42 to evaluate the change in signal-to-noise ratio (per Å) when the sky background is changed from dark (UVES spectrum) to that of the full-moon (taken from Patat 2004 for a 55° moon elevation at an angular distance of 30 degrees and a telescope airmass of 1.22). To also evaluate the feasibility of grey-time observations we have scaled the moon background (3.5 mag brighter than the dark sky in the B-band) by a factor 1/5 (equivalent to a background ~ 1.2 mag brighter than in dark conditions). The changes in S/N (relative to dark conditions) are shown in *Figure 31*; **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** for both Full and Quarter moon (thick and thin lines, respectively) and the Blue and Red arms. Results are shown for continuum magnitudes ranging from $r = 19-22.5$ mag.

Figure 31: Change in signal-to-noise ratio relative to the signal-to-noise ratio achievable under dark conditions as a function of wavelength for the two TARSIS ranges and for different r-band AB magnitudes. Solid lines indicate the results for $r = 19, 20, 21,$ and 22 mag and dashed lines indicate those for $r = 19.5, 20.5, 21.5,$ and 22.5 mag.

This figure shows that in, order to reach the CATARSIS scientific objectives, bright time is excluded. Grey time might be possible but when the moon illumination is below 50%. This could allow us, by adding ~ 4 extra nights per month (two per Quarter moon), to reduce the execution time from 6 years down to ~ 5 years depending also on final weather statistics.

Finally, we show in **Figure 32** some of the screen captures of the ETC-42 tool with the parameters used to derive the signal-to-noise ratio estimates given above regarding the "Instrument", "Site", "Source" and "Observing Parameters" configuration screens.

Figure 32: Top left: ETC-42 "Instrument" configuration screen. We also show the efficiency curve of the TARSIS Blue arm. Top right: ETC-42 "Site" configuration screen. The atmospheric transmission curve adopted is plotted. Bottom left: ETC-42 "Sources" configuration screen. The Sa galaxy template at $z=0.26$ is shown. Bottom right: ETC-42 "Observing Parameters" configuration screen. The resulting signal-to-noise ratio plot (per Å) obtained after running ETC-42 with the configuration described in previous panels is shown.